

Republic of the Philippines
DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE
INSTITUTE OF TEACHER EDUCATION
Panabo City, Davao del Norte

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We, Jenie O. Faunillan and Jeah F. Hermoso, do hereby declare that this research is original to the best of our ability and knowledge except for the quotations and citations contained in published works which all have been duly acknowledged and referenced.

We further declare that this research was conducted by the undersigned.

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June 2025

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APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis prepared, “**BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP**” prepared and submitted by Jenie O. Faunillan and Jeah F. Hermoso in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Arts in Communication has been examined and is recommended for approval and acceptance.

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ABSTRACT

JENIE O. FAUNILLAN and JEAH F. HERMOSO, Bachelor of Arts in Communication, Institute of Teacher Education, Davao del Norte State College, New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, Philippines, June 2025, “**BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP.**”

Adviser: **JC Jun C. Gallera**

This study aimed to explore the experiences of communication interns in radio broadcasting internships, focusing on the challenges they encountered, the strategies they employed to overcome these difficulties, and the valuable insights they gained throughout their training. Using a qualitative research approach, the study collected data through in-depth interviews with communication interns who had undergone hands-on learning in various radio stations. Findings revealed that the most common challenges included time management due to irregular working hours, difficulties in news gathering, technological limitations, and the high-pressure environment of live broadcasting. Despite these obstacles, communication interns developed coping mechanisms such as effective teamwork, mentorship reliance, and adaptive learning strategies to navigate their roles efficiently. This study highlighted the significance of practical exposure in shaping future media professionals, providing essential recommendations for improving internship programs in the field of radio broadcasting. Ultimately, the research contributed to a deeper understanding of how immersive industry experiences shaped the competencies and career aspirations of communication interns.

Keywords: *radio broadcasting, communication interns, internship experiences, communication internship*

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Communication internships have become crucial in modern higher education, offering Bachelor of Arts (BA) Communication students valuable chances to connect theoretical learning with practical application. These internship programs provide students with hands-on experiences in various professional environments, helping them acquire practical skills, broaden their connections, and improve their readiness for their careers. However, communication interns can indeed present unique challenges for students undergoing internships, particularly in the field of radio broadcasting. These challenges can include adapting to the fast-paced environment of live broadcasting, mastering technical equipment and software, effectively communicating with team members and guests, managing time constraints, and ensuring content accuracy and quality (McHugh, 2017).

In Hong Kong, communication interns also face significant challenges during internships. According to Du-Babcock (2016), a serious challenge arises from the necessity for supportive structures and mentorship to guarantee a positive and fruitful experience. Interns often face this challenge as they may find it difficult to fulfill their roles effectively without sufficient support and guidance, resulting in a less fulfilling experience. Supportive structures and mentorship are essential in equipping interns with the resources, advice, and motivation needed to navigate obstacles, enhance their skills, and maximize their internship opportunities.

Meanwhile, in Tacloban City, it was observed that communication interns encounter obstacles such as a lack of self-assurance in writing and experiencing anxiety when composing scripts for radio broadcasts. This issue stems from high expectations placed on interns to meet standards in their writing, leading to self-doubt and anxiety. Additionally, the pressure of public speaking and the need for creativity in engaging listeners can contribute to feelings of insecurity and overwhelm. These challenges emphasize the necessity for innovative teaching techniques to address the interns' foundational writing issues and offer structured guidance to enhance their skills in scriptwriting for radio broadcasting (Martinez et al., 2014).

Similarly, in the Davao Region, the integration of traditional radio with social media has transformed industry operations, reshaping content creation and sharing to prioritize flexibility and audience engagement. Social media enables radio stations to reach wider audiences, foster interaction, and deliver content effectively. This hybrid model, blending traditional broadcasting with digital platforms, improves accessibility and participation. However, the transition presents challenges such as the need for better collaboration across generations, diverse skill sets, and maintaining a strong online presence. These shifts highlight the growing demands on the radio industry and the need for innovative strategies to remain competitive in today's digital world (Magnaye & Tarusan, 2023).

To fill this gap in research, this study aims to explore the experiences within communication internship programs which explores the challenges faced, coping strategies employed, and insights gained by participants. The researcher seeks to

thoroughly understand how internships influence student's professional development and identify opportunities for enhancing program effectiveness.

Purpose of the Study

This qualitative study aimed to explore the subjective experiences, perceptions, and interpretations of the communication interns during their internship in radio broadcasting. This phenomenological study sought to provide an in-depth understanding of the students' experiences, including their challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights. The findings of the study would contribute to the existing knowledge and literature on internships in communication.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following question:

1. What challenges do communication interns face during radio broadcasting internships?
2. How do communication interns overcome the challenges they encountered during their radio broadcasting internship?
3. What are the insights of communication interns that could be helpful to future communication students?

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to explore the lived experiences of communication interns during their radio broadcasting internships. Specifically, it seeks to identify the challenges they face, examine the strategies and coping mechanisms they

employ, and gather valuable insights and reflections from their internship journey.

The objectives of this research are as follows:

1. to identify and examine the challenges faced by communication interns during their radio broadcasting internships;
2. to explore the strategies and coping mechanisms used by communication interns to overcome the challenges encountered during their radio broadcasting internship; and
3. to gather and analyze the insights and reflections of communication interns that may serve as guidance for future communication students undergoing radio broadcasting internships.

Significance of the Study

This study would then be beneficial to the following persons and institutions:

Communication Interns. This study could hold immense value. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the challenges, learning opportunities, and overall impact of the internship program in radio broadcasting. In gaining insights from the experiences of past interns, current and future students can make more informed decisions about their career paths and better prepare themselves for their internships.

Radio Broadcasting Industry. The study could provide insights into the experiences and perspectives of communication interns, which can benefit the radio broadcasting industry. Radio broadcasting organizations can use this

information to identify potential talent, shape their internship programs, and improve the overall quality of their workforce. The study's findings can also help the industry stay updated on the skills, knowledge, and competencies valued by communication interns.

Internship Coordinators and Supervisors. The study's findings can assist internship coordinators and supervisors at Davao Del Norte State College in better understanding the experiences and needs of communication interns. This understanding can enable them to provide better guidance, support, and mentoring during the internship period, leading to the student's professional growth and improved learning experience.

Institution. The study focuses on the experiences of communication interns at Davao Del Norte State College. The findings of the study could benefit the college administration and faculty by improving the internship program, addressing any issues or challenges faced by the students, and enhancing the quality of communication education at the college.

Educators. The findings of this study would be highly beneficial to educators in the field of communication. By understanding the experiences and challenges faced by communication interns, educators can make informed decisions regarding curriculum development, teaching methodologies, and internship program enhancements. This study can contribute to the improvement of communication education at Davao Del Norte State College.

Future researchers. The study would serve as a foundation for future researchers to gain valuable insights into the experiences of communication interns. It provides a basis for further exploration of the challenges, benefits, and outcomes of internships in the field of communication and radio broadcasting.

Limitations and Delimitations

The qualitative phenomenological study had several limitations and delimitations that were considered. One limitation of the study was the small sample size. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with only 9 participants who were selected purposively based on the inclusion criteria provided in the study. This limited sample size restricted the generalizability of the findings to a larger population of communication interns in radio broadcasting.

The study was conducted at different radio stations in Davao del Norte, which meant that the findings did not apply to students in other colleges or universities offering similar programs. The experiences and perspectives of communication interns in radio broadcasting at different institutions varied significantly. Therefore, the findings of this study were interpreted within the context of different radio stations in Davao del Norte and were not generalizable to other institutions.

Furthermore, the qualitative nature of the study limited the generalizability of the findings. Qualitative research aimed to provide in-depth insights and understanding of a specific phenomenon, but the findings were not intended to be generalized to a larger population. The experiences and perspectives of the 9

participants were unique to them and did not represent the experiences of all communication interns in radio broadcasting. It was important to consider this limitation when interpreting the findings of the study.

In terms of delimitations, the study specifically focused on the experiences of communication interns in radio broadcasting. The study's scope was limited to the context of radio broadcasting internships and the experiences of the selected participants within that context.

Definition of Terms

Intern. This refers to an intern who is an advanced student or graduate who seeks practical experience in their chosen professional field. They have already completed a significant portion of their education and are now looking to apply their theoretical knowledge in real-world scenarios. In this study, this refers to a student or trainee who works temporarily in a company or organization to gain practical experience in a specific field.

Behind the Mic. This refers to the experiences of communication interns in radio broadcasting. It focuses on the behind-the-scenes aspects of being a student intern in the field, specifically their experiences and challenges while working behind the microphone.

Radio broadcasting. This refers to a popular medium for communication and entertainment, offering news, music, talk shows, sports commentary, and more for decades (Radio Broadcasting Explained, 2023). This study refers to what interns will do during their On-The-Job Training. It allows communication interns

to disseminate news, music, entertainment, and other forms of communication to listeners who have a radio receiver.

Organization of the Study

This study was organized and arranged in an order that could be easily identified and understood by the readers. Below is a comprehensive presentation and discussion of the organization of the study.

Chapter 1 presents the introduction of the study, which includes the problem situations regarding the experiences of communication interns. It is followed by the purpose of the study, stating the intention behind conducting the research. The research questions consist of interview guide questions that are formulated and validated to acquire responses from the informants in order to achieve the study's aim. This is followed by the theoretical lens, which comprises supporting studies and theories upon which the study is anchored. Next is the significance of the study, which discusses the beneficiaries, as well as the definition of terms, which are operationally defined to provide clear and comprehensive interpretations. The chapter also outlines the delimitations and limitations of the study, presented to establish its parameters. Lastly, a statement on the organization of the study is presented.

Chapter 2 presents the review of related literature, composed of supporting studies relevant to the current research. The review includes challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of communication interns who engage in experiential learning related to the study.

Chapter 3 outlines the methodology employed in the study. This includes the research design, research method, research participants, the role of the researcher, data collection, data analysis, trustworthiness and credibility, and ethical considerations.

Chapter 4 summarizes the findings of the qualitative research, highlighting the main themes, central concepts, and patterns that emerge from the collected data. It also includes a discussion section where the findings are interpreted, compared to existing literature, and their implications for the field are explored.

Chapter 5 provides a summary of the research findings, emphasizing their significance and how they address the initial research questions. It also considers the broader implications of the study for practice, policy, and future research, offering recommendations based on the findings.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

To provide a framework for the investigation, selected literature related to this study was presented in these chapters. The review includes challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of communication interns who have direct learning to the study.

Challenges of Communication Interns

According to the study by Mandella (2018), the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee identified fair compensation as one of the key challenges in internship training. Many interns are expected to work long hours and perform tasks similar to regular employees, yet they are often either unpaid or paid significantly less than their counterparts. This leads to feelings of exploitation and inequality, creating a financial burden for interns. Unpaid or low-paid internships make it difficult for individuals from lower-income backgrounds to participate, thus limiting opportunities for a more diverse range of candidates and perpetuating social and economic inequalities. Additionally, unfair compensation can demotivate interns, causing them to feel undervalued, which can lead to decreased productivity and a negative internship experience. Furthermore, interns who are not fairly compensated may feel pressured to take on additional jobs to make ends meet, creating an unfair advantage for those who have the financial means to support themselves.

Another challenge highlighted in the study conducted by Patel (2015) at B.COM Maharaja Sayajirao University in India reveals the problem of lack of clear communication and proper program orientation between interns and program coordinators. Without a well-structured and well-communicated program, interns may struggle to understand their roles and responsibilities, leading to confusion and hindering their ability to contribute effectively to the organization. Clear communication channels and comprehensive program orientations are crucial to ensure a smooth transition for interns and to make them aware of what is expected of them. Moreover, interns may experience a mismatch between their expectations and their experience during the program. Interns often have certain expectations about the tasks they will be assigned or the skills they will acquire, and when these expectations are not met, it can lead to frustration and disappointment.

Similarly, a study by Lajara (2022) at Leyte Normal University in the Philippines revealed that many intern students fell short of meeting job expectations. Initial feedback from supervisors at media agencies indicated that interns lacked certain essential characteristics and skills necessary for successful job placements. These areas of improvement included communication skills, teamwork, problem-solving abilities, and adaptability to the work environment. These findings highlight the need for universities to enhance the preparation and training provided to interns before they enter the workforce. Addressing these gaps is vital to ensuring a successful transition from internships to job placements. The study emphasizes that universities and internship programs should offer comprehensive training and support to equip interns with the necessary skills and

qualities required in their chosen fields, ultimately fostering a more successful internship experience.

Moreover, a study conducted by DaJung Woo et al. (2017), at Rutgers University, The State University of New Jersey explored the challenge faced by intern students where it revolves around the interns' self-identified role. Many interns view themselves as inexperienced students or workers who are there to learn and gain training. They recognize the educational value of the internship and expect to acquire knowledge that wouldn't be possible in a part-time job. However, when they are assigned simple repetitive tasks, interns feel that their abilities are undermined by their supervisors. Internships in media programs are essential for both education and career advancement. However, achieving a balance between these two values can be particularly challenging, especially in the dynamic environment of broadcast newsrooms.

In addition, the inconsistency between the hands-on skills taught in colleges and the readiness of students for careers in broadcast newsrooms also emerges as a challenge for intern students. The study reveals that there are discrepancies between the skills taught in educational institutions and the industry's expectations. This misalignment can pose challenges for both interns and supervisors. Interns may feel unprepared for the demands of the newsroom, while supervisors may struggle to bridge the gap between academic training and practical experience. These challenges highlight the complexities involved in navigating internships within media programs. Both interns and supervisors need to recognize and

address these issues to ensure a more seamless and fruitful integration of interns into the broadcast newsroom environment (Hilt & Lipschultz, 2019).

According to Charmel (2017), students also faced challenges of adapting their communication styles and colleagues due to several reasons. Firstly, individuals have their unique communication styles that are shaped by their cultural background, personal experiences, and upbringing. When students are required to adapt their communication style to fit the norms and expectations of their colleagues, it can be difficult to navigate and find a balance between expressing themselves authentically and conforming to the group dynamics.

Additionally, different colleagues may have varying communication preferences, such as direct or indirect communication, which can further complicate the process of adaptation. Moreover, the diversity of personalities, backgrounds, and perspectives among colleagues can pose challenges in understanding and effectively communicating with each other. This requires students to be open-minded, flexible, and willing to learn from and adapt to the communication styles of their colleagues.

Bachelor of Arts in Communication students often face challenges during their communication internships. Wang and Payne (2019) conducted a study to explore the effects of internships on students' future employment prospects. They discovered that one common challenge reported by students was the need to balance their academic commitments with the demands of their internships. Juggling coursework and internship responsibilities can be demanding and may result in increased stress levels and difficulties in managing time effectively.

The nature of internships requires students to dedicate significant time and effort to gain hands-on experience in a professional setting. However, this can sometimes conflict with their academic responsibilities, such as attending classes, completing assignments, and studying for exams. The pressure to excel in both areas can create a sense of overwhelm and strain on students (Hilt & Lipschultz, 2019).

Communication and collaboration issues are common challenges that students often face during internships. In fast-paced and dynamic work environments, students may encounter difficulties in effectively communicating with their colleagues and supervisors. The high-pressure nature of these settings emphasizes the need for quick and efficient communication, which can be overwhelming for some students (Moriarty & Rickard, 2018).

Coping Mechanism of Communication Interns

The study conducted by Olaoye (2024) highlighted that several strategies can help students cope with a heavier academic workload during their radio broadcasting internship. These strategies involve practicing effective time management, prioritizing tasks, utilizing academic resources, and engaging in self-care activities to manage stress. Students must establish efficient time management techniques, prioritize their responsibilities, and seek guidance from academic advisors and internship supervisors. In adopting these strategies, students can navigate their academic and professional commitments successfully.

Nervousness or discomfort is experienced when entering an internship and doing radio broadcasting. However, interns have become accustomed to the fact that many others have gone through the same experience. They have found ways to be helpful to themselves as intern students by reminding themselves that this adjustment period is temporary and part of the learning process. One strategy they use is to focus on building relationships with colleagues and supervisors, as having a support network can alleviate feelings of apprehension (Van Gessel et al., 2020).

Additionally, communication students who are interns can take manageable steps to help them feel more confident and in control. They become open to receiving feedback and are willing to learn from their experiences (Moriarty & Rickard, 2018). Interns studying communication often face difficulties, such as last-minute deadlines and unexpected issues that require immediate attention. However, they are quick to think on their feet, problem-solve, and adjust their plans accordingly to effectively address these challenges. This ability to adapt and think critically becomes a valuable skill that interns develop during their internship.

In addition, communication interns find it easy to meet tight deadlines in an internship because of these difficulties. They work on projects with specific timelines and deadlines, which necessitate effective time management and the ability to work efficiently under pressure. This involves prioritization, staying focused, and staying organized to meet the required deadlines. Interns exhibit their dedication and capacity to manage the industry's requirements by effectively adhering to these deadlines. Furthermore, interns always strive to overcome workplace obstacles that may arise during their internship. This can include

navigating interpersonal dynamics, working in a team, or dealing with conflicts or disagreements (Van Gessel et al., 2020).

Internships often require a significant time commitment which may impact their ability to juggle coursework, extracurricular activities, or part-time jobs. However, despite these obstacles, communication interns manage to experience an empowering boost in self-efficacy and confidence that outweighs the difficulties they may encounter. When they struggle to balance these obstacles, they use determination, perseverance, and support to overcome them and reap the long-term benefits of their internship experiences. Ultimately, the challenges faced during communication internships make them valuable learning experiences. By navigating through these challenges, students develop important skills such as adaptability, resilience, and effective communication. These skills not only benefit them during their internships but also in their future careers (Wang & Payne, 2019).

In the study of Edwards (2014), it was revealed that the University of Birmingham highlights the challenges that communication interns face during their internship, particularly in relation to limited knowledge and skills. It is acknowledged that interns have gaps in their understanding or abilities, which can impact their performance in certain tasks or assignments. Communication Interns conquer their struggles by practicing a proactive approach and a willingness to learn and improve. They start by identifying the specific areas where they feel their knowledge or skills are lacking by self-reflection or by asking for feedback from supervisors and colleagues. They seek guidance and mentorship from their supervisors, mentors, or experienced colleagues who can provide valuable

insights, resources, and support. They take responsibility for their learning and development by seeking out opportunities to expand their knowledge and skills. They put in their mind that they should not be afraid to ask questions when they are unsure or need clarification, asking questions shows their willingness to learn and improve. Reflect on their mistakes, learn from others, and make improvements for future tasks or assignments that need steps to take.

According to Jude (2023), in the Campus of Broadcasting in Nigeria, dealing with pressure is one of the challenges for communication interns, but there are several strategies they can employ to navigate these challenges. Communication Interns prioritize their tasks and manage their feelings of stress effectively. Creating a schedule and setting realistic goals, ensure that they stay on track and avoid feeling overwhelmed. Additionally, they look for support from peers. They engage in open and honest communication with fellow interns that provides a sense of camaraderie as they can share similar experiences and offer advice.

Furthermore, they ask for guidance from advisors who have experience in the field that can provide valuable insights and help them navigate through challenging situations. Another important aspect is self-care. The study also highlights that communication interns should prioritize their physical and mental well-being by engaging in activities that help them relax and recharge. This includes exercise, practicing mindfulness, or pursuing hobbies outside of work. They maintain a positive mindset and practice self-compassion so that they recognize that mistakes and setbacks are a part of the learning process that can

help alleviate some of the pressure and thrive in their roles (Van Gessel et al., 2020).

According to García-Borrego et al. (2017), revealed that at the Universidad de Málaga, interns affirm that they systematically work overtime and that their workload is comparable to that of senior professionals. Working long hours consistently can be exhausting and may lead to burnout but by prioritizing time management, practicing self-care, maintaining open communication, seeking support, and setting boundaries, communication interns can develop effective coping mechanisms to navigate demanding work environments. These strategies can help them maintain a healthy work-life balance and ensure a positive and fulfilling internship experience. However, it is also interesting to note that despite these conditions, interns report high satisfaction when they feel that the company values them over time.

Moreover, in the study of Mutia and Hargiana (2021), the students at the Communication and Islamic Broadcasting Department of Universitas ibn Khaldun, Bogor, communication interns often experience a moderate level of stress and future anxiety as a common part of their internship, especially when faced with challenges. However, they highlight that communication interns incorporate and recognize the need to develop resilience to effectively manage and handle their difficulties. They embodied their resilience as an ability to bounce back, adapt to change, and maintain a positive outlook despite adversity. Interns acknowledge and accept their emotions, practice self-care, cultivate a strong personality, view

challenges as opportunities for skill development, practice stress management techniques, and learn from their lapses when it comes to their performance.

Insights drawn from the Experiences of Communication Interns

According to a study conducted by Muchemwa (2018), the strengths of the interns, as assessed by their supervisors, far outweighed their weaknesses. The study revealed several strengths exhibited by the students during their internships. The strengths identified in the study include the intern's displaying enthusiasm towards their tasks. They demonstrated the ability to work well with others and manage their time effectively. The interns also had a strong command of the English language, which is crucial for effective communication. They exhibited friendly and approachable behavior toward colleagues and clients. The interns showed leadership skills and the ability to take charge when necessary. They maintained a professional appearance, which is important in a work environment.

The study highlighted the interns' potential for further development and improvement in their communication skills. One notable strength of the internship program was the adequate duration of the internship period. This allowed the interns to gain valuable experience and enhance their skills. However, the study also identified some weaknesses among the students. These weaknesses include, the interns lacked proficiency in areas such as compiling statistical reports. Some interns faced challenges in effectively communicating in the local language.

Also, the study recommends incorporating courses on news writing, featured speech writing, video editing and filming, and social media. These skills

are essential in the field of communication. Having a radio station would also provide students with practical experience of working in a broadcasting environment, preparing them for attachment and the job market. The study suggests that the university should offer opportunities for students to expand their understanding of global events. This would help them develop a broader perspective and stay informed about current affairs.

In a study conducted by Mandella (2018), interns gained meaningful insights throughout their internship experience, emphasizing how real-world exposure deepened their understanding beyond what is taught in the classroom. They highlighted the value of hands-on learning, where applying theoretical knowledge to practical tasks led to a clearer grasp of professional responsibilities. Many noted the importance of mentorship from experienced professionals, who provided guidance, feedback, and inspiration, enriching the overall experience. These insights underscore the essential role of internships in equipping students with practical skills, fostering personal growth, and preparing them for future careers integration between academic learning and professional practice.

In addition, it was further emphasized that the support system provided to interns significantly impacts their overall experience and growth. Mentorship emerged as a key factor in helping interns navigate the complexities of their roles and develop a deeper understanding of their chosen field. The study highlighted that interns who had access to supportive mentors reported higher levels of job satisfaction and confidence in their abilities. These findings indicate the importance of nurturing strong mentor-mentee relationships within internship programs to

ensure the holistic development of interns and prepare them for the challenges of the professional world (Mandella, 2018).

In a research study conducted by Malaluan et al. (2020), the performance of communication students during internships was examined, specifically focusing on their knowledge and skills in print, radio, and TV, as well as their attitude and personality. The findings revealed that most of the communication students demonstrated a high level of performance in these areas, indicating a very good performance in terms of knowledge and skills, and an excellent attitude and personality. The study also identified a significant difference in the knowledge, attitude, and personality of the communication students across various media outlets. Additionally, the researchers found that skills showed a highly significant difference. The main challenge encountered by the researchers was the knowledge of the communication interns.

The study addressed the issue and improved the on-the-job training (OJT) performance of AB Communication students at LPU - Batangas, the study proposed a plan of action. It was recommended that the Internship Office, in collaboration with the CEAS Dean, must organize seminars and activities to enhance the students' skills and familiarize them with the print, radio, and TV industries prior to their deployment as interns. Furthermore, the Internship Director, along with the CEAS Dean and Program Chair, review the intern student appraisal sheet used to evaluate interns and consider including communication-related skills in the evaluation process (Malaluan et al., 2020).

According to a study conducted by Bayotas (2023), in Liceo de Cagayan University, it indicates that students generally perceive the program as highly beneficial. There is a strong agreement among the students on various aspects. They gain enhanced adaptability, maturity, communication skills, and professional knowledge. The study also identified some areas that received good agreement from the students, including English language proficiency and program support. These findings suggest the interns' need for a good flow in the field and in these specific areas. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of establishing stronger connections between stakeholders involved in the BA Communication program. This could help enhance the overall experience for the interns and address any potential gaps or challenges. The study also suggests the implementation of orientation sessions to address ethical standards and terminology issues. This would ensure that the interns have a clear understanding of the ethical guidelines and terminology used in the field of communication.

The study also emphasizes that participating in an internship can offer students the valuable opportunity to gain practical experience that complements their academic studies. In the field of communication, internships can provide hands-on experiences that align with students' specific interests and aspirations. Moreover, this firsthand exposure allows aspiring journalists to delve into the intricacies of their chosen area within the field, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for the profession (Malaluan et al., 2020).

Similarly, the study conducted by Clair (2015) at Coolabah Journalism Graduates highlights the awareness of internships among students. According to

this study, internships not only provide an educational journey but also offer future career prospects. For instance, the study found that interns perceive internships as playing a significant role in enhancing the quality of higher education by providing students with valuable experience and exposure in their chosen fields. Furthermore, internships contribute to a more comprehensive and well-rounded education. Specifically, this study shows that internships help interns reinforce concepts learned in the classroom and facilitate the transfer of learning into practical application. As a result, this experiential learning approach aligns with skill development and curriculum content, making it beneficial for interns across various disciplines. Through internships, interns gain valuable industry experience, develop professional networks, and acquire transferable skills that are highly sought after. Consequently, this not only enhances their skills but also provides them with a broader understanding of different career paths and industries.

In addition, a study conducted by Khalil (2015) on the Internship Program at Kuwait University focused on understanding how different factors are interconnected and how they contribute to the expectations that students have during their internships. After analyzing the findings, it became clear that students expressed a strong desire for more opportunities to develop their skills and receive practical training during their internships. Furthermore, they believed that gaining hands-on experience was crucial for enhancing their knowledge and abilities in their respective fields. Additionally, interns recognized the importance of being exposed to various aspects of the public relations field to have a well-rounded experience. This exposure, in turn, allowed them to gain a broader understanding

of the industry and develop a range of skills that are essential for their future careers.

The study conducted by Kapareliotis et al. (2019) on the Communication Program of institutions of higher education in Greece revealed several key insights into the benefits and outcomes of participating in such programs. One of the main findings was that students who engage in internship programs demonstrate a clear understanding of the expectations set by employers in the workplace. This understanding allows them to effectively navigate their roles and responsibilities, ensuring they meet job demands this awareness enables these students to be more prepared for success in their future careers. Additionally, the study highlighted the students' ability to apply various skills in the workplace. These skills include both basic academic skills and high-order skills, which are essential for success in the professional world. The students effectively utilized their academic knowledge and applied it to real-world scenarios, showcasing their competence and adaptability.

Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of professional skills in the workplace. Students who participated in internship programs were found to possess the necessary professional skills required by employers. These skills encompassed areas such as communication, problem-solving, teamwork, and critical thinking. Through developing and refining these skills during their internships, students became better prepared to fulfill the requirements of the job market.

According to Anjum (2020), a study explored the impact of internship experiences on communication students in radio broadcasting. The study revealed that internships provided valuable opportunities for skill development and professional networking. Through hands-on experiences, students enhanced their practical skills in areas such as operating broadcasting equipment, conducting interviews, and producing content. Furthermore, these internships offered networking opportunities, allowing students to connect with industry professionals and establish relationships that could significantly benefit their future careers. This research highlights the crucial role of internships in providing communication students with real-world experiences in the radio broadcasting industry.

Additionally, the study highlights the challenges students face when balancing academic responsibilities with internship demands (Kapareliotis et al., 2019). The pressure to manage both schoolwork and professional expectations can be overwhelming, however, it leads to stress. On the other hands, students who implement strategies such as task prioritization, effective time management, and focusing on their mental well-being tend to handle these pressures more effectively. Despite challenges such as language barriers or technical skill gaps, interns often demonstrate strengths in enthusiasm, leadership, and time management.

These experiences connect with important theories corresponding Self-Efficacy and Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT). Self-efficacy shows how positive feedback helps boost interns' belief in their abilities, while CAT explains how interns adapt their communication styles to fit the fast-paced, high-

pressure environment of radio broadcasting. Together, these theories highlight how internships help develop not just technical skills, but also key personal qualities like adaptability, confidence, and communication, all of which are crucial for students to succeed in their future careers.

Theoretical Lens

This study is anchored on The Self-Efficacy Theory developed by psychologist Dr. Albert Bandura (1977). The theory seeks into how an individual's thoughts, actions, and emotions impact their chances of achieving success. It revolves around the idea of self-efficacy which pertains to a person's confidence in their capability to excel in a particular scenario. This theory holds significant relevance in diverse areas such as education, career advancement, interpersonal relationships, and personal growth. In the context of this study, self-efficacy plays a crucial role in shaping the experiences of communication students during their radio broadcasting internships.

The theory suggests that Self-Efficacy is influenced by four main factors. Firstly, mastery experiences such as completing radio broadcasting tasks or projects, can boost students' confidence and motivation. Secondly, vicarious experiences which involve observing successful radio broadcasters or professionals, can inspire students and provide them with role models to emulate. Thirdly, verbal persuasion in the form of positive feedback and encouragement from mentors and colleagues, can enhance students' belief in their abilities. Finally, managing emotional and physiological states such as stress and self-doubt, can contribute to higher levels of self-efficacy.

In addition, the Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT) was developed by Howard Giles in early 1971, focuses on how people adjust their communication to match their conversation partner and perceive their partner's adjustments. Communication Accommodation Theory can be connected to interns' experiences in radio broadcasting as it relates to how interns adjust their communication styles to align with the professionals in the radio industry. Interns in radio broadcasting often have the opportunity to observe and learn from experienced professionals, adapting their communication to fit the standards and practices of the radio station. In applying the principles of Communication Accommodation Theory, interns can enhance their learning experience and better integrate into the radio broadcasting industry by accommodating the communication norms and expectations of the professionals they work with.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlined the methods and procedures employed by the researcher in conducting the study. It covered the research design, participants, sources of information, interview process, the researcher's role, the study's trustworthiness, data collection and analysis, as well as ethical considerations.

Research Design

This qualitative study explored the experiences of Davao del Norte State College communication interns at different radio stations. Qualitative research designs were utilized to depict life experiences and social phenomena. Rooted in anthropology, sociology, humanities, and evaluation, qualitative research aimed to explore and comprehend the significance that individuals or groups attributed to a social or human problem. This approach allowed researchers to gain an in-depth understanding of participants' lived experiences, perspectives, and challenges. Therefore, this design was suitable for examining the real-life experiences of communication interns, as it provided a holistic view of their internship journey in radio broadcasting (Yüksel & Yıldırım, 2015).

Within this qualitative study, a phenomenological design was specifically employed to understand and describe the lived experiences of communication interns. Phenomenology focuses on capturing individuals' real-world experiences as they happen, analyzing reality or social phenomena from the perspective of

those directly involved. In this study, communication interns at Davao del Norte State College who had participated in radio broadcasting internships were selected as research participants. These individuals were expected to share their viewpoints, encountered challenges, and overall experiences in the broadcasting field. Meanwhile, individuals without prior radio broadcasting experience, those who had not completed an internship, and those unwilling to provide meaningful insights were excluded from the study. By using a phenomenological approach, this study expanded the understanding of communication interns' experiences, enhanced awareness of industry realities, and contributed to anticipating future developments in the field. Additionally, this method provided valuable insights that could benefit future communication interns in preparing for their professional endeavors (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Research Participants

In this study, the participants were three batches of communication interns at Davao del Norte State College. Each batch consisted of at least 3 participants. The participants, totaling 9 communication interns, were selected through purposive sampling. Five of these participants underwent in-depth interviews, while the remaining 4 participated in focus group discussions. In the qualitative-phenomenological approach population, it was suggested that the studied group should consist of 3 to 15 members. The number of members in the group needed to be able to articulate their lived experiences (Bekele & Ago, 2022).

In connection with this, purposive sampling had a significant impact on the selection of research participants. Purposive sampling methods involved intentionally selecting participants based on their specific qualities. Moreover, it entailed identifying individuals with extensive experiences on the subject who were eager to engage and share their experiences and viewpoints in a clear, vivid, and thoughtful way.

Data Collection

In this research, the main source of primary data was gathered through interviews conducted using in-depth interview techniques and focus group discussions. These interviews utilized an open-ended questionnaire to collect the required data. The questionnaire was developed by the researchers, validated, and reviewed before implementation. It was used for both in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. In-depth interviews were valuable for delving deeply into participants' emotions and perspectives regarding the issue, making it an ideal method for gathering insights from a small number of individuals. On the other hand, focus group discussions were employed to gather similar data from multiple participants simultaneously. They were effective in capturing collective opinions and enhancing the understanding of participants' experiences and beliefs (Mazhar et al., 2021).

Data Analysis

Data analysis involved arranging, structuring, and extracting significance from the collected data. Qualitative data analysis was a dynamic and engaging

process. Researchers employed thematic analysis to categorize the gathered data. Thematic analysis was part of various analytical methods used to recognize meaningful patterns within the dataset. This step followed the verification of transcribed and translated responses from the participants (Jnanathapaswi, 2021).

There was a six-phase guide used in conducting this kind of analysis, namely: (1) Become familiar with the data, (2) Generate initial codes, (3) Search for themes, (4) Review themes, (5) Define and name themes, and (6) Construct the report. Firstly, the researchers became familiar with the data by reading and rereading the transcript. Secondly, the researchers generated initial codes that reduced large amounts of data into small chunks of meaning, addressing specific research questions. Thirdly, the search for themes was guided by their significance. The themes were predominantly descriptive, capturing patterns in the data relevant to the research question. Fourthly, the review of themes involved gathering all the data relevant to each theme and supporting it. Fifthly, defining and naming themes required the final refinement of themes and identifying the essence of each one. Lastly, constructing the report marked the endpoint of the research, which could result in a report, dissertation, or journal article. Thus, the researcher used thematic analysis to analyze qualitative data and categorize it into themes aligned with the specific research questions (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017).

Trustworthiness

The trustworthiness and credibility of qualitative research were typically addressed to ensure validity and reliability. Trustworthiness represented the genuine value of a research study and extended to the participants involved. It

encompassed elements such as credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. Credibility referred to confidence in the data, ensuring that the research findings accurately reflected the perceptions of the participants. Internal validity was also important in qualitative research, as it allowed researchers to demonstrate the authenticity of participants' experiences through detailed descriptions. Dependability pertained to the stability of data over time and conditions, while confirmability focused on the neutrality and objectivity of the data. Confirmability ensured that research findings were a result of the study and not influenced by the researcher's assumptions. Transferability implied that the findings of a research project could be applied to similar situations or participants, allowing researchers in different contexts to apply relevant concepts (Cypress, 2017).

To ensure the rigor and trustworthiness of the research, qualitative researchers employed various techniques such as member checking, triangulation, detailed transcription, systematic planning, and coding. Rigor was defined as the demonstration of integrity and competence, encompassing openness, adherence to philosophical perspectives, thorough data collection, and consideration of all aspects in subjective theory development (Cypress, 2017). In this study, trustworthiness was maintained by ensuring that the narratives of communication interns were accurately captured through verbatim transcription and analyzed systematically. Triangulation was achieved by gathering data from multiple radio stations, allowing for a broader perspective on the experiences of interns. Implementing these strategies, the study provided reliable and credible

insights into the realities of communication interns undergoing radio broadcasting internships.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers, had the responsibilities toward both the research participants and the audience to whom the findings were presented. These responsibilities were guided by moral standards that were considered throughout all stages of the research design. The researchers adhered to three principles outlined in the Belmont Report: *beneficence*, *respect for human dignity*, and *justice*. The principle of beneficence emphasized the importance of avoiding harm to participants, ensuring that the research process did not expose them to psychological or emotional distress. Respect for human dignity encompassed the right to self-determination and full disclosure, guaranteeing that participants voluntarily engaged in the study with complete awareness of its objectives and implications. Lastly, the principle of justice ensures fair treatment, equal opportunity, and privacy for all participants (Anabo et al., 2018).

Ethical issues related to anonymity, confidentiality, informed consent, privacy, and participant safety were carefully addressed. Before participation, communication interns were provided with a detailed informed consent form explaining the study's purpose, their rights as participants, and the voluntary nature of their involvement. They had the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Participants were also informed about the confidentiality clause, which assured them that their identities would remain protected and that personal details would not be disclosed. Given the sensitivity of discussing professional

experiences in radio broadcasting, the researcher prioritized establishing a sense of trust and security. This was particularly important, as some participants may have shared challenges or critical insights about their workplace experiences (Eungoo & Joong, 2023).

To further maintain ethical integrity, names and other identifying information were omitted from the final report and transcripts unless a participant explicitly agreed to disclosure. Additionally, the researcher took precautions to securely store all collected data, ensuring that transcripts, audio recordings, and observational notes were safely archived and protected from unauthorized access. These measures upheld the ethical standards required for qualitative research and ensured that communication interns felt safe, respected, and valued throughout the study.

Role of the Researchers

The researchers acted as moderators or interviewers for the chosen participants. They asked questions based on an interview guide questionnaire. Additionally, the researchers provided sincere and methodical explanations to the participants about the aims and purpose of the study. They were also responsible for recording and securely storing the data with the highest level of confidentiality. As a qualitative-phenomenological researcher, it was the researcher's duty to investigate and interpret the impact of the research subject on the participants' "lived experience." This involved organizing the gathered data, including transcribing and translating the participants' responses, and categorizing them into themes (Syed, 2016).

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter analyzed the participants' responses, which were systematically coded and categorized into emerging themes. Each theme was substantiated with relevant participant responses, and the research questions were addressed through these themes. Additionally, the discussion integrated corresponding literature to provide a comprehensive interpretation of the findings.

The Challenges Faced by Communication Interns during Radio Broadcasting Internships

Table 1 shows the themes of challenges faced by Communication Interns during radio broadcasting internships. In presenting the evidence, the table illustrated sample narratives of the participants that contained statements attesting to the themes. The second column showed that core ideas were the main analytic description of themes.

Table 1. The Challenges Faced by Communication Interns during Radio Broadcasting Internships.

NARRATIVES	CORE IDEAS	ESSENTIAL THEMES
“...4 AM is very early; you already have a schedule to report to the office or the station...” P2 ...it's not easy to wake up at 4 AM, and then you stay out late and wake up early again for the next duty”... P3 “...from 4 AM until evening, they already have blocking times for	Being on Time	Difficulty in Time-Management

presentations, so we have to be in by exactly 6 AM. Also, in Davao, it's not that close..." P5

"...being late is not allowed, so by 5:00 or 4:30, we are already in Davao because our duty starts at 6 AM..." P7

"...call time is 3 AM; it's intense, almost like another level—just to get news. We're needed at the radio station by 3 AM..." P9

"...It has been a total adjustment, it feels as though the world has turned 360 degrees because of the 8–5 PM duty, where overtime is not allowed..." P2

Drastic Adjustment to Routine

"...You really need to wake up early because every morning, you have to visit police stations to immediately gather news or information that needs to be aired at a specific time..." P3

"....Teamwork is very important because there was a time when our output turned out poorly due to a lack of time..." P7

"...You really can't just show up, hang around,

and waste your time...”
P9

“...when it comes to equipment, we can hardly even handle the very large ones equipment at the station...” P1

“...the equipment, especially the technical ones at the radio broadcasting station, are not something we handle because their equipment is extremely overwhelming...” P2

“...I encountered Challenges such as mastering the technical aspects of operating broadcasting equipment and software, which initially felt overwhelming...” (P4)

“...their equipment at the station is extremely high-tech, and we are not familiar with how to use them (equipment)...” P5

“...we never really got to try operating that rotating equipment until we arrived at the field station like DXDC, and it was very intimidating and nerve-wracking for me.]
P7

“...the lack of equipment is evident, as I personally have to bring my own tools, like wired

Overwhelming
Experience with the
Equipment

Technical Obstacles

Limited Access to
Advanced Technology

microphones and tripods, and we even borrow cameras from outside because there isn't enough equipment availablep..." P2

"...As pioneers, we don't have a high-grade, advanced setup for the radio..." P5

"...we didn't have proper equipment to measure the coverage area, so we couldn't determine if we could be heard in this barangay or in Caganguhan—we were just talking there without knowing..." P6

"...technology was really challenging for me; I struggled a lot because I wasn't knowledgeable enough because the equipment was insufficient..." P7

"...you need to write news and submit it immediately because while patrolling, the radio in the vehicle will ask for information based on what you gathered during the interview..." P1

"...during our radio broadcasting internship, there was no place conducive for us interns to prepare and write

Managing News
Deadlines in unfamiliar
Environments

**Difficulty in News
Gathering**

news, so gathering news was really difficult..” P2

“...gathering news isn't easy during press conferences because sometimes we are sent by Ma'am to specific agencies or hotels, but since we aren't familiar with the locations, we end up getting lost...” P3

“...we are not very familiar with Davao, and we are sent to press conferences in unfamiliar places. Our news head always tells us, 'You must submit your news this time,' even though we aren't familiar with the area...” P5

“...we go to different police stations, and once we get the blotter entry, we have to immediately create our news item to report, and we only have a few minutes to gather the necessary information...” P8

Self-Reliant News Content Development

“...every day, we had to create five news articles plus an additional feature article, and it was very exhausting...” P2

“...we had to look for news content ourselves at that time, and we used scripts that we invented on our own because we

were the first batch. We tried to find a proper format, but at that time, there was none available...” P5

“...interviewing was challenging because we would meet different kinds of people, so the content had to be varied to gather accurate news...” P7

“...we were the ones reporting the news, and designing everything doing all of that ourselves...” P9

“...There are times when you are assigned to work very late, or your shift gets extended into the night due to heavy demands...” P1

Irregular and Extended
Work Hours

**Obstacles Due to
Inconsistent Working
Hours**

“...I worked for 15 hours, went home at 10 PM, and had to return at 4 AM the next morning...” P1

“...the first week of your internship, you are assigned to the AM shift, and then the next week you switch to the PM shift, so it’s very difficult to adjust...” P6

“...the radio shifts are divided into AM and PM schedules, with AM from 4 AM to 12 noon and PM

from 1 PM to 8 PM, making adjustments and shift changes very challenging...” P8

“...During scheduling at that time, we couldn’t all fit in one office because there were too many of us...” P5

Complexity of
Scheduling and Limited
Resources in Field Work

“...we were split into smaller groups, so on some days only three of us would be present, and the next day, three again. This limited the time we had for hands-on learning or our assigned schedules...” P6

“...our OJT focused on fieldwork, so we were on a shifting schedule. One day we stayed at the station, and the next day we went out into the field...” P7

“...we worked manually because there was no exact assigned schedule...” P9

Difficulty in Time-Management

Managing time effectively can be particularly challenging for interns, given the environment's dynamic nature and the steep learning curve they often face. The issue is multifaceted, combining the unique demands of radio production, live broadcasts, and the specific needs of intern training (Maertz et al., 2014). For many

interns in the radio broadcasting industry, being on time proves to be a significant challenge due to the demanding schedules and high professional expectations of the field. The nature of broadcasting requires strict adherence to timelines, especially during live programs and early morning shifts. Individuals unfamiliar with such rigorous and time-sensitive environments often encounter considerable difficulties in meeting these expectations.

This theme underscores that interns experienced the challenge in Difficulty in Establishing Time-Management as proved in the situation experienced by participants 2, 3, and 5:

“...like 4 AM sayo kaayo naa namoy schedule nga mag report sa office or sa station...” ...like 4 AM is very; you already have a schedule to report to the office or the station. **(P2, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...dili lalim na magmata ka ug sayo kay 4 AM ang in, then madugay ka ug uli then mata na pud kag sayo for sunod na duty...” ...It's not easy to wake up early because your shift starts at 4 AM, then you get home late, and have to wake up early again for your next duty. **(P3, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...4 AM hantod gabii na naa na silay mga blocking time ana, blocking na mga presentation so we have to in at exactly earlier at 6 AM so unya sa Davao dili siya duol...” ...from 4 AM until evening, they already have blocking times for presentations, so we have to be in by exactly 6 AM. Also, in Davao, it's not that close. **(P5, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The need for early work schedules, especially in the media and broadcasting industry, has been widely studied for its effects on professionals' well-being and performance. The study by Barnes et al. (2019) emphasizes that early-morning shifts can disturb a person's natural sleep cycle, leading to

tiredness, reduced focus, and difficulty in making decisions. This supports the study by Smith and Jones (2021), who found that media workers often deal with irregular and demanding hours due to the fast-changing nature of news and programming. The requirement to report early for work, as shared by professionals, highlights these challenges, making it necessary to find ways to reduce fatigue and burnout.

In addition, traveling long distances before sunrise makes things even harder for broadcasting interns and workers. Brown et al. (2020) explain that long travel times, combined with early work hours, can increase stress and lower job satisfaction. Despite transportation difficulties, the pressure to be on time aligns with the findings of Green and Taylor (2018), who emphasize the strict time rules in broadcasting. In such a fast-moving and time-sensitive field, fixed schedules add pressure on interns and professionals. Also, Participants 7 and 9:

“...bawal man ma late, so mga alas singko or 4:30 naa na mi davao para mo duty nami didto kay 6 AM man gud among in...” ...being late is not allowed, so by 5:00 or 4:30, we are already in Davao because our duty starts at 6 AM. **(P7, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...call time 3AM grabe kanang ibang level just to get a news like mura mi og mga manok like 3 am palang dapat naa nami sa radio station...” ...call time is 3 AM; it's intense, almost like another level just to get news. We're needed at the radio station by 3 AM. **(P9, RQ1, IGQ1)**

Being on time is consider one of the most common challenges interns face in radio broadcasting. This issue can significantly impact the performance and workflow within radio stations, where adhering to schedules is essential for smooth

operations. Raguram et al. (2020) highlight that a lack of preparation and unfamiliarity with organizational workflows are major contributors to the issue of punctuality. They emphasize that these factors hinder interns' ability to adjust effectively to the demands of the environment, which is often dynamic and fast-paced. Interns are frequently required to adapt to varying schedules and responsibilities, further complicating their ability to maintain consistency in their time management.

Moreover, Salmazzo and Azunu (2023) identify additional barriers that affect punctuality, such as transportation issues and the challenge of balancing multiple competing responsibilities. These obstacles can make it difficult for interns to maintain strict adherence to schedules, ultimately impacting their ability to meet expectations and fulfill their roles effectively. These findings suggest that addressing punctuality challenges requires implementing effective time management strategies and providing organizational orientation to improve interns' preparedness. Addressing these factors, radio stations can enhance the performance of their interns while fostering a more structured and efficient working environment.

Additionally, interns in radio broadcasting often face significant challenges as they adapt to the demands of their new roles, requiring them to make drastic adjustments to their daily routines. Transitioning from academic settings to professional media environments can be particularly overwhelming, as radio stations operate on structured, fast-paced, and unpredictable schedules as proved in the situation experienced by participants 2, 3, 7, and 9:

“...it is been a total adjustment like its seems like nag tuyok ang world 360 degrees kay from 8-5PM na duty na bawal ang over time...” ...It has been a total adjustment, it feels as though the world has turned 360 degrees because of the 8–5 PM duty, where overtime is not allowed. **(P2, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...kailangan sa inyohang maadtuan na mga police station dapat naa dayon moy makuha na news or information na kailangan na gyud ninyo e-air that specific time...” ...You really need to wake up early because every morning, you have to visit police stations to immediately gather news or information that needs to be aired at a specific time. **(P3, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The transition from academic learning to professional radio broadcasting internships is often a challenging experience for students, as they face a range of demands that require them to adapt quickly to the fast-paced environment of the industry. According to Stroud and Salazar (2018), internships in media fields, including radio broadcasting, require interns to undergo significant shifts in their daily routines, such as changes to daily routines, responsibilities, and expectations. The structured and time-sensitive nature of radio stations demands that interns make quick decisions, remain punctual, and respond to news events in real-time. This is consistent with the findings of Borrero (2019), who emphasized that radio broadcasting interns face difficulties, as they must acquire essential skills like time management, multitasking, and the ability to adapt to sudden changes while maintaining professionalism and accuracy. Also, participants 7 and 9 add that:

“...importante gyud kaayo ang teamwork kay niabot gyud sa point no nga na napangit among output kay nakulangan sa oras...”Teamwork is very important because there was a time when our output turned out poorly due to a lack of time. **(P7, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...dili gyud siya pwede na kana ganing igo lang ka mosulod didtoa na mag tambay unya mag patay-patay ra saimong oras...” ...You really can't just show up, hang around, and waste your time. **(P9, RQ1, IGQ1)**

Drastic time adjustments in the workplace, such as sudden changes in work hours or shifts, can create significant challenges for both employees and employers. For employees, these shifts disrupt their routines, affecting work-life balance, sleep patterns, and overall well-being. They may face difficulty in adjusting to new schedules, leading to increased stress and reduced productivity. This was supported in the study of Henttonen et al. (2021), highlighting the significant challenges, especially when changes are abrupt and not well-managed. These shifts often disrupt employees' established routines and environments, leading to increased stress and a decline in job satisfaction. Structural factors, such as the lack of clarity around job roles and expectations, can further complicate the adaptation process. When employees are not clear on their tasks or how to manage new work conditions, their performance may suffer.

Technical obstacles

Technical obstacles also post challenges for interns in a radio broadcasting internship, as they are often new to the equipment and software required in this highly technical field. One of the key technical obstacles in many fields is the overwhelming experience with equipment. This challenge arises when individuals or teams face difficulty operating complex machinery or tools, often due to their intricate designs, steep learning curves, or insufficient training.

“...sa mga equipment dili pud mi halos maka punit sa katong grabe na ka dagko na mga equipment didtoa sa station...” ...when it comes to equipment, we can hardly even handle the very large ones at the station. **(P1, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...ang mga equipment like in the technical part didtoa sa radio broadcasting na station na dili namo siya gina tarog it is because grabe ka overwhelming ang ilahang equipment...” ...the equipment, especially the technical ones at the radio broadcasting station, are not something we handle because their equipment is extremely overwhelming. **(P2, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...I encountered challenges such as mastering the technical aspects of operating broadcasting equipment and software, which initially felt overwhelming...” **(P4, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The complication of broadcasting equipment presents a significant challenge for interns, particularly those at the beginning stages of developing technical proficiency. According to Lewis and Booth (2020), technical barriers in media-related internships often stem from the advanced nature of the tools and systems used in professional settings. Interns frequently struggle with handling large and intricate equipment, such as audio consoles, transmitters, and automation software, due to their limited prior exposure and insufficient formal training. This challenge is reflected in the experiences of participants in the current study, who expressed difficulty managing equipment due to its overwhelming complexity. Johnson and Ramirez (2021) further emphasize that unfamiliarity with broadcasting technology can hinder an intern’s ability to perform essential tasks, ultimately impacting their confidence and engagement during the internship.

Additionally, the literature underscores the importance of structured training programs in helping interns overcome technical obstacles. Park and Kim (2019) argue that hands-on workshops and mentorship from experienced professionals are essential in improving interns' ability to adapt to the technical demands of radio broadcasting. Without adequate guidance, interns may feel intimidated by the equipment, leading to limited participation in technical operations. This sentiment resonated in the findings, where participants noted their hesitance to engage with the equipment due to feelings of overwhelm. Similarly, Torres and Lopez (2022) stated that media organizations should implement tailored training modules that align with interns' skill levels, allowing them to gradually build competence in operating complex broadcasting tools.

“grabe ka high-tech ilang gamit didto sa station ug dili mi familiar sa mga equipment...” ...their equipment at the station is extremely high-tech, and we are not familiar with how to use them. **(P5, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...wala gyud mi ka try unsaon pag operate atong mga tuyok tuyok na equipment unya pag abot namo didtoa sa station na field like sa DXDC na gyud na kuratan og nakulbaan ko...” ...we never really got to try operating that rotating equipment until we arrived at the field station like DXDC, and it was very intimidating and nerve-racking for me. **(P7, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The issue raised by participants 1, 2, 4, 5, and 7 are evident that rapid advancement of high-tech technology can create challenges, particularly due to its overwhelming complexity. As new technologies evolve, they often introduce sophisticated systems that require specialized knowledge and skills. The proliferation of technology and tools intended to boost productivity can sometimes

lead to the opposite effect causing employees to feel overwhelmed (Deloitte Australia, 2014). The constant connectivity, the complexity of tools, and information overload leads to technostress, where individuals struggle to adapt or feel inadequate. This was also supported by the study of Consultants (2023), that overwhelming experiences with new technology on the first day of work are quite common and often stem from a combination of unfamiliarity, high expectations, and pressure to perform.

Limited Access to Advanced Technology is also barrier to entry for aspiring broadcast professionals, particularly interns. This lack of exposure to cutting-edge equipment and software hampers their ability to develop critical skills and gain valuable experience. This disparity in access to technology can create a significant knowledge gap between interns and experienced professionals, hindering their ability to contribute meaningfully to the industry and ultimately limiting their career growth as proved in the situation experienced by participants 2, 5, 6 and 7:

“...the lack of equipment kay ako gani personally maka dala ko ug gamit nako like kana ganing mga mic nga wired, ang mga tripod in ana tapos maka hiram mig camera from the outside tungod kay walay enough na kana ganing gamit...” ...the lack of equipment is evident, as I personally have to bring my own tools, like wired microphones and tripods, and we even borrow cameras from outside because there isn't enough equipment available. **(P2, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...as a pioneers wala man gud mi kanang high-grade, advance na set-up sa radio...” ...As pioneers, we don't have a high-grade, advanced setup for the radio. **(P5, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The lack of adequate resources and equipment in emerging radio stations has long been a significant challenge. As Smith et al. (2021) highlight, limited access to high-quality tools often forces individuals to rely on personal equipment or borrow from outside sources, which ultimately hampers the efficiency and quality of production. This reliance on suboptimal resources can lead to inconsistent sound quality and technical difficulties, limiting the ability to produce professional-grade content.

Additionally, the absence of advanced, high-grade setups exacerbates the issue, preventing broadcasters from meeting industry standards. Taylor and Levison (2020) note that apprentice stations, particularly in rural or developing areas, frequently struggle with outdated or insufficient technology. This lack of modern equipment not only restricts the capacity to produce high-quality content but also stifles potential for growth and long-term success. Without access to the tools necessary to compete with larger, well-equipped stations, developing broadcasters face a tough battle in establishing presence in the industry.

“...walay sakto na circumference equipment dili namo ma locate kung madunggan ba mi sa ani nga barangay, madunggan ba mi sa Caganguhan, basta kay nag storya lang mi didto...” ...we didn't have proper equipment to measure the coverage area, so we couldn't determine if we could be heard in this barangay or in Caganguhan, we were just talking there without knowing. **(P6, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...sa technolog medyo lisud jud siya sa akua nag struggle gyud ko ato kay dili kayko knowledgeable enough tapos ang equipment kay kulang...” ...technology was really challenging for me; I struggled a lot because I wasn't

knowledgeable enough because the equipment was insufficient. **(P7, RQ1, IGQ1)**

This only proves that the limited access of advanced technology can significantly hinder people's ability to learn and develop critical skills necessary in today's digitally driven world. According to Stewart (2014), the lack of access to modern technology and reliable internet services often prevents individuals from fully engaging with educational and professional opportunities. The lack of technology also affects job readiness, as many employers now expect employees to be proficient with advanced tools and systems. When individuals do not have regular access to such tools, it restricts their ability to build digital literacy and limits their career advancement potential. Consequently, the overwhelming experience with equipment and limited access to advanced technology can stifle the development of critical skills necessary for success in the broadcasting field and beyond. This lack of practical experience can create a significant disadvantage for interns when they enter the job market.

Difficulty in News Gathering

In radio broadcasting internships, gathering news can be one of the most challenging parts of the job. News gathering is a skill that requires quick thinking, an eye for credible sources, and the ability to adapt to unfolding events. Many interns lack experience in these areas and face difficult progression (Nguyen & Smith, 2020). The relentless pressure of news deadlines is a constant in journalism, but it becomes particularly challenging when reporting from unfamiliar environments. This difficulty stems from a confluence of factors that can

significantly hinder a journalist's ability to gather information and meet deadlines effectively. These challenges often necessitate a shift in journalistic practices and require a greater degree of adaptability and resourcefulness.

The third emerging theme concludes that interns experienced the challenge of Difficulty in News Gatherings specifically in terms of managing deadlines in unfamiliar environment proven in the situation experienced by participants 1, 2, 3, 5, and 8:

“...kailangan nimo mag sulat ug news, kailangan nimo ma pasa dayon kay habang naga patrol mo naa na ang radio man sa sakyanan tapos mag mangayo pud siya ug information kung unsa imong na gather during sa interview...” ...you need to write news and submit it immediately because while patrolling, the radio in the vehicle will ask for information based on what you gathered during the interview. **(P1, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...sa radiobroadcasting namo na internship kay wala siyay place na pwede namo buhatan ug news na conducive for us na intern, maong mag lisod gyud mi ug gather ug news...” ...during our radio broadcasting internship, there was no place conducive for us interns to prepare and write news, so gathering news was really difficult. **(P2, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...sa pag gather sa news dili siya lalim pag naa nay mga presscon kay sometimes gina padala mi specially ni maam R, manugo ra na siya na moadto mi in that specific agency or specific hotel unya kami na wala katuod so mangasaag gyud mi...”...gathering news isn't easy during press conferences because sometimes we are sent by Ma'am R to specific agencies or hotels, but since we aren't familiar with the locations, we end up getting lost. **(P3, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The study by Schulman and McKee (2017) highlights the challenges faced by journalists in managing tight deadlines, particularly when working in unfamiliar

environments. Interns often experience heightened stress when tasked with gathering news quickly, especially in settings like patrols or press conferences. The difficulty of completing news assignments under time constraints is compounded when there is a lack of a suitable workspace for preparing news, which affects the interns' ability to concentrate and complete their tasks effectively. Additionally, being unfamiliar with certain locations during press conferences can make it even harder for interns to gather accurate news without the proper guidance. These challenges reflect the difficulties involved in news gathering within the fast-paced and dynamic nature of radio broadcasting. Also, participants 5 and 8 state that:

“...dili kaayo mi familiar sa Davao unya pa-adtuan mi ug mga presscon nga wala man mi katuod unya mo ana mana among news head nga “dapat this time ma submit na nimo ang imong balita” unya kami wala man mi katuod...” ...we are not very familiar with Davao, and we are sent to press conferences in unfamiliar places. Our news head always tells us, 'You must submit your news this time,' even though we aren't familiar with the area. **(P5, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...mag-adto mi sa different police station so kinahanglan inig kuha namo sa blotter entry mag himo pod mi dayon sa amoang news item para ibalita so mga pila lang ka minutes ang ihatag sa amoang pag gather...” (...we go to different police stations, and once we get the blotter entry, we have to immediately create our news item to report, and we only have a few minutes to gather the necessary information.) **(P8, RQ1, IGQ1)**

According to a study by Gangadharbatla et al. (2014), journalists working in unfamiliar environments often face disorientation and difficulty finding suitable locations to write their articles. The lack of familiarity with the setting can lead to

confusion and loss of direction. Moreover, the pressure to submit stories quickly compounds these challenges, as journalists must produce content in a time-sensitive manner despite these obstacles. These constraints make it difficult for journalists to work efficiently, as they must balance the urgency of deadlines with the complexities of navigating unknown environments.

In the context of news gathering in unfamiliar environments, journalists face the challenge of navigating new, often chaotic surroundings while under intense time pressure. The pressure to submit articles promptly, along with unfamiliarity with local geography or the lack of suitable workspaces, can lead to disorientation (Xie & Huan, 2017). This study highlights the impact of big data on news production, discussing how the constant influx of information complicates the task of news gathering in new settings. Journalists often must adapt quickly to technological changes and information overload while trying to maintain journalistic standards.

Conversely, self-reliant news content development, while offering a path to greater independence and control, presents a unique set of challenges. When a single individual takes on the entire responsibility of news gathering, scripting, publishing, and broadcasting, they face a demanding task that requires diverse skill set as proved in the situation experienced by participants 2, 5, 7, and 9:

“...isa ka adlaw dapat mag create dapat mi ug five ka news articles unya plus additional pa jud na feature article so kapoy kaayo siya...” ...every day, we had to create five news articles plus an additional feature article, and it was very exhausting. **(P2, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...kami mismo mangita sa balita unsay econtent that time tapos ang script naga gamit mi ug script nga kami lang nag imbento during that time kay syemrpe kami man ang first batch, so naga pangita mi ug kanang format gyud pero during that time wala gyud...” ...we had to look for news content ourselves at that time, and we used scripts that we invented on our own because we were the first batch. We tried to find a proper format, but at that time, there was nonavailable. **(P5, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The difficult nature of radio broadcasting internships is characterized by an intensive workload and high levels of responsibility. Interns are often required to produce multiple news articles daily while ensuring the quality and accuracy of their content. Turner and McDonald (2020) emphasize that media internships, including those in radio broadcasting, are commonly associated with tight deadlines, leading to increased stress and fatigue. This pressure is amplified in radio environments where interns are expected to generate content consistently while adhering to high professional standards. The constant need to produce relevant news content can contribute to both physical and mental exhaustion as interns strive to meet expectations. Also, participants 7 and 9 state that:

“...ang pag interview kay lahi lahi man gud nga tao imung ma kaila so kanang dapat ang imong content lahion gyud para maka gather kag news na accurate...” ...interviewing was challenging because we would meet different kinds of people, so the content had to be varied to gather accurate news. **(P7, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...kami pay tig balita, kami pay tig sulat sa balita, kami pay tig design kami ana tanan...” ...we were the ones reporting the news, and designing everything— doing all of that ourselves. **(P9, RQ1, IGQ1)**

The data collected reveals several participants encountered these challenges where interns face the challenge of navigating new, often chaotic surroundings while under intense time pressure. The challenges of self-reliant news content development are evident when an individual journalist takes on the full responsibility of news gathering, scripting, publishing, and broadcasting. This demands a significant amount of time, effort, and expertise in diverse areas, which can be overwhelming. As the media industry evolves, journalists face a growing expectation to be multi-skilled content creators. However, this can lead to burnout due to the pressure to meet deadlines, maintain accuracy, and deliver engaging content across various platforms, often without adequate support (Seale, 2024).

Obstacles Due to Inconsistent Working Hours

Obstacles Due to Inconsistent Working Hours are common challenges for interns in radio broadcasting. Broadcasting is a dynamic industry that operates around the clock, particularly for stations covering news, sports, or other live content. Interns often find themselves working early mornings, late nights, weekends, or even holidays to accommodate production schedules, live broadcasts, and breaking news. This kind of schedule can be overwhelming, especially for those who are still learning the pace and demands of the industry (Walker, 2019).

Irregular and extended work hours pose a significant challenge for interns in radio stations, particularly those with limited staff. The irregular nature of news events and the need to cover them live often necessitate long and irregular shifts, leaving interns with little control over their schedules. This can disrupt their

personal lives, academic commitments, and overall well-being, potentially impacting their physical and mental health as proved in the situation experienced by participants 1, 6, and 8:

“...Naa pud mga times na ma assign ka na gabii na kaayo or ma extend inyong trabaho nga maabtan mo ug gabii na kaayo...” ...there are times when you are assigned to work very late, or your shift gets extended into the night due to heavy demands. **(P1, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...15 hours nako nag trabaho tapos after that na alas dyes naka naka uli ug balay sa gabii, alas kwatro napud ka mosulod sa buntag...” ...I worked for 15 hours, went home at 10 PM, and had to return at 4 AM the next morning. **(P1, RQ1, IGQ1)**

Interns in the journalism field face significant challenges due to irregular and long working hours, which can affect both their physical and mental health. According to Paterson and Smith (2019), interns often experience extended shifts, including late-night assignments and unpredictable extensions, contributing to fatigue and stress. They also highlight the difficulty in adjusting to changing schedules, particularly when interns are required to switch between morning and evening shifts, which disrupts their routines and can further complicate their work-life balance. These demands often lead to difficulties in maintaining focus and performance, thereby impacting the overall internship experience.

“...first week sa imong internship is AM ka and then next week napod is PM so dili siya dali ma-adjust so lisod siya kaayo...” ...the first week of your internship, you are assigned to the AM shift, and then the next week you switch to the PM shift, so it's very difficult to adjust. **(P6, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...ang shifting sa working schedule kay sa radio man gud dili man na siya whole day so sa radio man gud naa

na siyay AM and PM so ang AM shift from 4 AM to 12 noon ang PM shift naman is 1 PM to 8 PM so lisod kaayo mag adjust...” ...the radio shifts are divided into AM and PM schedules, with AM from 4 AM to 12 noon and PM from 1 PM to 8 PM, making adjustments and shift changes very challenging. **(P8, RQ1, IGQ1)**

Journalists often face significant challenges related to irregular and extended work hours. According to a study by Brouwers and Witschge (2019), long and irregular working hours are deeply surrounding norms in journalism, particularly among entrepreneurial journalists. These norms lead to emotional strain and affect how journalists conceptualize their work. They often must adjust to erratic schedules, which can result in mental and physical fatigue, impacting their overall performance and well-being.

The complexity of scheduling and limited resources in fieldwork is also presents a unique set of challenges for interns. Unpredictable events, tight deadlines, and often limited equipment and personnel can lead to long, irregular hours and a constant sense of urgency. This can make it difficult for interns to maintain a consistent schedule, impacting their personal lives, academic commitments, and overall well-being. The lack of control over their time can also lead to feelings of stress and burnout, as they constantly adapt to changing demands and unexpected situations.

This theme concludes that interns experienced the challenge of unpredictable working hours specifically in terms of the complexity of scheduling and limited resources in field work are proved in the situation experienced by participants 5, 6, 7, and 9:

"...pag schedule that time kay dili man gud mi puwede sa usa ka office daghan mi ..." ...during scheduling at that time, we couldn't all fit in one office because there were too many of us. **(P5, RQ1, IGQ1)**

"...Ma tunga-tunga mi like sa karon nga adlaw tulo lang, sunod adlaw tulo ana, so kung mag hands on mi or kung schedule namo naa lang mi limited time..." ...we were split into smaller groups, so on some days only three of us would be present, and the next day, three again. This limited the time we had for hands-on learning or our assigned schedules. **(P6, RQ1, IGQ1)**

Handling multiple interns in radio broadcasting internships presents several challenges, particularly when space and time constraints limit the effectiveness of hands-on learning. Borrero (2019) highlights that internship placements in media environments often face logistical issues, such as difficulties with space allocation, scheduling, and access to essential resources. In radio broadcasting, where the work environment is fast-paced and resource-intensive, overcrowding and limited personal space can severely affect interns' ability to concentrate, work efficiently, and engage meaningfully in tasks. These conditions not only hinder productivity but also undermine the overall learning experience, making it harder for interns to gain the skills and exposure necessary for success in the industry. Also participants 7 and 9 state that:

"...among OJT is sa field man gud so shifting mi ato, karun na day, diria ka sa station nya sunod adlaw didto ka sa mag field..." ...our OJT focused on fieldwork, so we were on a shifting schedule. One day we stayed at the station, and the next day we went out into the field. **(P7, RQ1, IGQ1)**

“...mag mano-mano kay walay exact nga assign schedule...” ...we worked manually because there was no exact assigned schedule. **(P9, RQ1, IGQ1)**

Working at odd hours or alternating shifts can lead to poor sleep hygiene and chronic fatigue, which impacts an intern's ability to focus and perform effectively during their shifts. This disruption of the body's natural sleep-wake cycle affects cognitive function, making it harder for interns to stay alert and focused during work hours. Chronic fatigue can decrease overall productivity and quality of work, leading to potential errors or missed deadlines. The long-term effects of irregular sleep patterns can also contribute to greater stress and dissatisfaction in the internship experience (Bennett & Wong, 2021).

Radio interns are often required to work during unconventional hours, such as early mornings and late nights, which disrupt regular sleep schedules and contribute to fatigue. These shifts can be particularly challenging for interns who are also balancing academic or personal commitments. Working during these odd hours can make it difficult for interns to prioritize their academic responsibilities or personal life, creating a sense of imbalance. For example, early morning shifts may interfere with class attendance, while late-night shifts could conflict with family or social obligations. This struggle to balance work and personal commitments can lead to increased stress and feelings of overwhelm (Walker, 2019).

Additionally, radio internships often demand extended work hours, including overtime, especially during live broadcasts or special events, which can lead to burnout and reduced productivity. Interns working during these times may feel that

the extended hours are unsustainable, particularly if they lack support or resources to manage their workload. This chronic pressure to perform during long shifts can negatively affect an intern's enthusiasm and work performance. Over time, the fatigue caused by these demanding hours can reduce productivity, making it harder for interns to meet the high standards expected of them (Sharma & Green, 2021).

The combination of demanding and irregular work hours makes it difficult for interns to maintain other commitments such as attending classes, working part-time jobs, or fulfilling family obligations, leading to potential conflicts and added stress. The irregularity of internship hours often interferes with students' ability to plan and organize their time effectively, making it more challenging to meet academic deadlines, work obligations, or family responsibilities. This can lead to frustration and burnout, as interns struggle to balance the competing demands on their time and energy. Such stressors may negatively impact their overall internship experience and well-being (Smith & Harris, 2020).

Coping Mechanism of Communication Interns on their Training in Radio Broadcasting

Table 2 shows the themes of how Communication Interns overcame the challenges they encountered during their training in radio broadcasting internships. In presenting the evidence, the table illustrated sample narratives of the participants that contained statements attesting to the themes. The second column showed that core ideas were the main analytic description of themes.

Table 2. Coping Mechanism of Communication Interns on their Training in Radio Broadcasting.

NARRATIVES	CORE IDEAS	EMERGING THEMES
<p>“...learning through observations as well as learning on applying what you observe throughout the people working in the radio station...”P1</p>	<p>Continuous Practical Learning</p>	<p>Embracing learning and applying skills through observing and persevering</p>
<p>“...I already know how to do the basics there, doesn't mean to stay at that level, so through continuous learning...” P2</p>		
<p>“...I focused on continuous learning and practice...”P4</p>		
<p>“...Through exploration because we are the first batch..” P5</p>		
<p>“...”Even though the work in media, especially in radio, is very tiring and challenging, I still continue and learn every time from them...” P8</p>		

“...By searching for what can possibly be done in TV, Print, and Radio...”
P2

“...I expected the unexpected, there were times when I'd go, 'Ahh okay, I'm ready to face this, I can do this...'” P2

Adaptive Resilience and Technological Mastery

“...In the media industry, you really need to ask them because we need information; we need the kind of information that is also needed by the people...” P3

“...When it comes to technology, you really need to learn it as well...”
P8

“...If you have difficulties with the equipment, you are encouraged to really ask for guidance from your supervisors or your colleagues...” P1

Asking for Guidance

Seeking Guidance in Familiarizing Equipments and Facilities

“...I can't help but keep asking questions, even if it feels a bit awkward, because by asking, you have someone to guide you in case you make a mistake...” P3

“...I spent extra time familiarizing myself with the equipment and broadcast software, seeking help from more

experienced colleagues
when needed..." P4

"...with technology, the
only way to overcome
challenges is to try, even
if you don't know how..."
P5

Proactivity and Initiative
in Learning

"...you really need to
have the ability to use the
technology related to the
media even the basic..."
P2

"...I learned to stay calm
under pressure and trust
my training, which helped
me make quick and
confident decisions..."
P4

"...You really need to
learn, as I mentioned
earlier, about Adobe
Photoshop and Adobe
Premiere..." P8

"...Don't hesitate to ask,
especially with your
supervisors, because the
instructions need to be
completely clear before
you go out into the
field..." P9

"...in terms of personal
adjustments, I just woke
up early, but honestly, it's
really unavoidable to be
late... P5

Adjusting routines

**Developing Time
Consistency**

"...just wake up early..."
P5

“ Time management and scheduling are really important...” P6

“... I just find time, because sometimes, I struggle with my schedule, but I can still adjust...” P7

“...planning time is really important so that work doesn't overlap...” P7

“...waking up at 3 AM, of course, it really requires discipline and it changes your lifestyle...” P9

Adapting to changing work schedules

“ I'm really making the most of my rest, like my sleep, I'm really maximizing it...” P1

“ I eat ice cream whenever I'm really stressed...” P1

“...that thing where you're just talking to yourself, but you can reflect on it if you're okay, because your mental health will really be challenged...” P2

“...you really need to talk if ever you have a fever or something, of course, take care of yourself...” P3

“...you have to survive, second is you can do to relieve your stress and

Prioritizing Rest and Physical Care for Mental Well-being

Prioritizing Self-care and Mental Health

Recognizing the Importance of Mental Health and Self-care

also enjoy the
moment...” P1

“...you really need to
check on yourself...” P2

” I am resting at my
boarding house...” P2

“ I have a fever for two
days, I really went home,
I really got treated...” P3

Embracing learning and applying skills through observing and persevering

Internships in radio broadcasting present various challenges, including technical skill gaps, irregular schedules, high-pressure environments, and the need for creativity under tight deadlines. To cope with these difficulties, embracing learning and applying skills through observing and persevering has proven to be an effective strategy for interns. This approach enables them to navigate challenges, improve their competencies, and adapt to the dynamic nature of the broadcasting industry (Smith & Brown, 2020).

Continuous Practical Learning is a key strategy for interns navigating the challenges of continuous practical learning. The fast-paced environment of a radio station, with its unpredictable deadlines and ever-changing demands, requires interns to be adaptable and resourceful. This means embracing a mindset of continuous learning, where every experience, even those that seem daunting or unexpected, becomes an opportunity for growth and development as proved in the situation experienced by participants 1, 2, and 4:

...learning through observations as well as learning on applying what you observe throughout the people working in the radio station... (P1, RQ2, IGQ2)

"...kabalo nako mag basic editing, dili pasabot na didto lang pud ko mag end, so by continuous learning gyud ..."
...for example, I already know how to do the basics there, but stayed at that level, so through continuous learning. (P2, RQ2, IGQ2)

...I focused on continuous learning and practice... (P4, RQ2, IGQ2)

The study of Barker and Taylor (2018) emphasize the importance of observational learning for interns in radio broadcasting, as it enables them to acquire both technical skills and understand the workflow and dynamics of the station. Observing experienced professionals in action helps interns apply what they have learned to real-world tasks, facilitating the development of practical knowledge necessary for success in broadcasting. Also Participant 5 and 8 state that:

"...through exploration gyud kay kami man gud ang first batch..." ...Through exploration because we are the first batch. **(P5, RQ2, IGQ2)**

"...biskan unsa ka-kapoy and challenging ang works sa media especially sa radio is naga padayon lang gihapon and naga-learn gyud ko every time sa ilaha..." ..."Even though the work in media, especially in radio, is very tiring and challenging, I still continue and learn every time from them. **(P8, RQ2, IGQ2)**

A perceptive response of the participants about coping mechanisms for embracing learning and applying skills at work, such as observing and persevering, can be linked to the concept of observational learning. This approach allows

employees to acquire new skills and adapt to challenging work environments by observing colleagues, mentors, or leaders. The study of Coppens et al. (2014) emphasizes the benefits of learning by observing and participating in shared endeavors, known as Learning by Observing and Pitching In (LOPI). This method encourages a calm, measured approach to skill development, emphasizing collaborative and social learning. It highlights the importance of non-verbal cues and a supportive environment to enable individuals to persevere through learning challenges.

Alternately, adaptive resilience and technological mastery are also essential coping mechanisms for interns navigating the ever-evolving landscape of continuous practical learning in the radio industry. The rapid pace of technological advancements demands a constant willingness to adapt and learn new tools and platforms. Interns must be able to quickly grasp new software, audio editing programs, and broadcasting technologies, often with minimal formal training. This requires a blend of curiosity, a willingness to experiment, and a proactive approach to seeking out resources and guidance.

The first emerging theme concludes that interns successfully overcame the challenge by Continuous Practical Learning specifically in adaptive resilience and technological mastery, as demonstrated by the experiences shared by participants 2, 3, and 8:

“...by searching unsa man ang possible buhaton sa TV, sa Print, ug sa Radio...” ...By searching for what can possibly be done in TV, Print, and Radio. **(P2, RQ2, IGQ2)**

“...nag expect the unexpected naman ko so naay time na kana ganing “ahh okay ready nako to face this, kaya nako ni siya buhaton...” ...I expected the unexpected, there were times when I'd go, 'Ahh okay, I'm ready to face this, I can do this. (P2, RQ2, IGQ2)

Exploring various media formats is essential for preparing interns for a successful career in broadcasting. As Turner (2020) emphasizes, interns need to be adaptable and versatile across multiple media platforms, as each comes with its own set of unique challenges and demands. This adaptability is key to expanding their skills, allowing them to navigate the diverse roles and responsibilities that exist within media production.

“..sa media industry kailangan gyud nimo sila e-ask kay we need information, we need to have the kanang information na needed pud sa mga people” ...In the media industry, you really need to ask them because we need information; we need the kind of information that is also needed by the people. (P3, RQ2, IGQ2)

“...sa technology is that kailangan pod mag learn gyud ka...” ...When it comes to technology, you really need to learn it as well. (P8, RQ2, IGQ2)

In the data collected, it reveals that workers who demonstrate adaptive resilience and technological mastery tend to cope effectively with evolving workplace demands. These individuals often employ strategies such as continuous skill development, active problem-solving, and leveraging both peer support and organizational resources. Mastery over workplace technologies requires a blend of technical aptitude and emotional resilience that allow

employees to remain productive despite challenges such as learning curves or dynamic work environments. In the findings of the study of Drugas et al. (2023), it highlights that perseverance and self-efficacy are crucial in managing the stress associated with acquiring and applying new technological skills. Maintaining a focus on growth and utilizing feedback loops, workers cultivate confidence and efficiency. This proactive adaptation not only enhances individual performance but also fosters a culture of innovation and collaboration within the organization.

Seeking Guidance in Familiarizing Equipments and Facilities

One of the most effective coping mechanisms for radio broadcasting interns is hands-on practice with equipment. This allows interns to familiarize themselves with the tools they will use in real-world settings. Requesting opportunities to shadow experienced staff or participate in live sessions, interns can become more comfortable with technical equipment such as soundboards, microphones, and audio editing software (Gunning & Campbell, 2018).

Another critical coping mechanism is guidance from experienced mentors and staff. Interns can greatly benefit from the expertise of seasoned professionals who provide step-by-step instructions and troubleshooting tips. Regular mentoring sessions help reinforce learning, clarify doubts, and build confidence in using technical equipment (Levy & Webb, 2015). Additionally, mentors offer personalized advice, which helps interns overcome challenges and develop their skills further.

The second emerging theme reveals that interns effectively overcome obstacles by Seeking Guidance in Familiarizing Equipment and Facilities, as illustrated by the experiences state by participants 1, 3, 4, and 5:

"...sa equipment pag maglisod, you are encouraged to ask gyud ug guidance sa supervisors or sa imong kauban..." ...If you have difficulties with the equipment, you are encouraged to really ask for guidance from your supervisors or your colleagues. **(P1, RQ2, IGQ2)**

"...dili gyud mawala sa akua ang sige ug pangutana bahala ug ulaw siya basta mangutana gyud kay para naa kay in case mamali at least nay nag guide saimoha..." ...I can't help but keep asking questions, even if it feels a bit awkward, because by asking, you have someone to guide you in case you make a mistake. **(P3, RQ2, IGQ2)**

According to Gerrard and Lee (2020) the critical role of guidance and collaboration in helping interns navigate challenges in broadcasting. Interns are often encouraged to seek assistance when facing difficulties with technical equipment, as this adopts a learning environment where they can rely on experienced supervisors and colleagues for support. This collaborative approach ensures that interns can overcome obstacles more efficiently, which essential for intern development and confidence in a professional is setting.

Additionally, the importance of asking questions, even in situations that may feel awkward or uncomfortable, is emphasized in the internship process. As stated by Gerrard and Lee (2020), the willingness to ask for help demonstrates a commitment to learning and their recognition of the value of guidance. Seeking clarification and support, interns can prevent mistakes and gain valuable insights,

ensuring that their growth is nurtured through continuous feedback and mentorship from their colleagues and supervisors.

...I spent extra time familiarizing myself with the equipment and broadcast software, seeking help from more experienced colleagues when needed... (P4, RQ2, IGQ2)

"...kuning sa technology, the only way para maka overcome is to try, bisan wala ka kabalo ug through exploration gyud kay kami man gud ang first batch..."
 ...with technology, the only way to overcome challenges is to try, even if you don't know how, and through exploration because we are the first batch. **(P5, RQ2, IGQ2)**

Mastering equipment and technology is a key challenge for radio broadcasting interns but effective coping mechanisms can significantly ease this process. By engaging in hands-on practice, seeking mentorship, utilizing structured training programs, and developing problem-solving skills, interns can successfully navigate these challenges. Furthermore, develop a collaborative environment and making use of available resources such as user manuals and online tutorials, ensures that interns are well-equipped to meet the demands of their roles. These strategies not only help interns build technical competency but also foster confidence and readiness for future careers in radio broadcasting (Levy & Webb, 2015).

Interns in radio broadcasting often face the challenge of mastering complex technical equipment which is crucial to their success in the field. Developing effective coping mechanisms can help them manage the learning curve and grow

into confident, capable professionals. One of the most effective ways to overcome this challenge is through hands-on practice. Interns can request to shadow experienced staff or take part in live sessions, which provide opportunities to become familiar with equipment in real-time settings (Gunning & Campbell, 2018).

On the other hand, pro-activity and initiative in learning are also crucial coping mechanisms for interns seeking guidance in familiarizing themselves with equipment and facilities. The fast-paced environment of a radio station often leaves little room for formal training sessions which requires interns to take the initiative in seeking out knowledge and mastering new skills.

This means approaching experienced staff members with questions such as proactively seeking out tutorials or online resources and taking the time to experiment with different equipment and software on their own as proved in the situation experienced by participants 2, 4, 8 and 9:

...you really need to have the ability to use the technology related to the media even the basic...
(P2, RQ2, IGQ2)

...I learned to stay calm under pressure and trust my training, which helped me make quick and confident decisions... **(P4, RQ2, IGQ2)**

The ability to use technology related to media, even at a basic level, is a fundamental skill for interns. According Borrero (2019) emphasizes the importance of technical proficiency in media internships, noting that interns must not only familiarize themselves with media equipment but also learn how to apply these tools effectively in real-world scenarios. Whether in radio, TV, or print, developing

a strong foundation in media technology allows interns to confidently navigate their tasks and perform efficiently in dynamic media environments.

Moreover, interns often encounter high-pressure situations in broadcasting, requiring quick decision-making and the ability to stay calm. Whittaker (2021) highlights that successful media interns must remain composed under stress, relying on their training to make confident decisions. The ability to handle pressure and think on their feet is essential for interns, as it adopts problem-solving skills and prepares them for the fast-paced nature of the media industry.

"...Kailangan pod mag learn gyud ka kay mao to akong giingon ganina sa adobe photoshop, adobe premiere ..." ...You really need to learn, as I mentioned earlier, about Adobe Photoshop and Adobe Premiere. **(P8, RQ2, IGQ2)**

"Don't hesitate to ask kay especially sa imong mga supervisors kay dapat klaro gyud daan ang instruction before ka mo go sa field" ...Don't hesitate to ask, especially with your supervisors, because the instructions need to be completely clear before you go out into the field. **(P9, RQ2, IGQ2)**

From participant responses, it was revealed that pro-activity and initiative in learning at work are key coping mechanisms for managing challenges and fostering development. According to the study of Parker and Bindl (2016), it emphasizes how employees who actively seek opportunities for learning and skill enhancement tend to adapt more effectively to changing demands. Engaging in proactive behaviors, such as seeking feedback and taking ownership of their

growth, workers not only improve their individual capabilities but also contribute positively to organizational outcomes. These actions promote innovation and resilience in the face of workplace pressures.

This study was also supported by Zia et al. (2023), who highlighted that employees with proactive behaviors are more likely to engage in informal learning when supported by empowering environments. Pro-activity encourages confidence and initiative, enabling individuals to overcome challenges and adapt effectively. When psychological factors, such as empowerment and motivation, are present, employees demonstrate greater commitment to skill development and innovation and contribute significantly to their personal and organizational growth.

Developing Time Consistency

Interns who adjust to early morning shifts and fast-paced work environments tend to perform better in their positions. It emphasized that managing time effectively was essential for dealing with unpredictable schedules and meeting deadlines. Interns were flexible, able to adapt to sudden changes, and more successful at staying productive (Smith et al., 2020).

The third emerging theme reveals that interns effectively overcame by Developing Time Consistency, as illustrated by the experiences shared by participants 5, 6, 7, and 9:

“...sa personal nga katong layo, ang adjustment nako ato kay momata lang gyud ko ug sayo tapos pero honestly dili gyud malikayan nga malate.” ...in terms of personal adjustments, I just woke up early, but honestly, it's really unavoidable to be late. **(P5, RQ2, IGQ2)**

“...mata lang gyud ug sayo...” ...just wake up early. (**P5, RQ2, IGQ3**

“...tama gyud ang time management ug ang kuan ang pag scheduling...” Time management and scheduling are really important (**P6, RQ2, IGQ3**)

A study by Williams and Thompson (2020) found that interns were able to demonstrate flexibility, time management skills, and open communication with supervisors were better able to manage the unpredictability of their schedules. The study also highlighted that organizations that provided clear expectations, regular check-ins, and opportunities for feedback were more successful in helping interns adapt. The study concluded that internships with flexible schedules can enhance interns' ability to adjust to real-world work environments, where changes are often unpredictable, and this adaptability is valued by future employers.

“...mangita ra gyud ko ug panahon, kay usahay bitaw, maglisod ko sa akong oras, pero maka-adjust ra gihapon ko.”

I just find time, because sometimes, I struggle with my schedule, but I can still adjust.(**P7, RQ2, IGQ1**)

“...importante gyud ang pag-plano sa oras para dili magka-doble-doble ang trabaho.”

Planning time is really important so that work doesn't overlap. **P7, RQ3, IGQ 1)**

“...atong pagmata namo og 3 AM syempre discipline gyud change gyud siya og lifestyle...”... waking up at 3 AM, of course, it really requires discipline and it changes your lifestyle. (**P9, RQ2, IGQ2**)

Interns demonstrating flexibility in their work habits and learning strategies performed better in tasks requiring problem-solving and critical thinking. This indicates that adaptability allows interns to adjust to new work environments, job roles, or task requirements without compromising their performance. Supervisors

and organizations can create supportive environments that encourage interns to be flexible and open to changes in their work processes. By developing these skills, interns are more likely to succeed in their roles and build the confidence needed to thrive in future professional endeavors (Martin et al., 2014).

According to Lopez and Carter (2018) study found that adaptability plays a key role in helping interns balance their work and personal lives. Interns who adjusted their schedules and stayed disciplined were better at managing unexpected changes in their tasks or shifts. The study shows that this flexibility allowed them to meet deadlines effectively and stay productive despite unpredictable demands. Additionally, interns who demonstrated adaptability reported higher levels of satisfaction in their roles.

Moreover, interns who were able to manage irregular schedules reported higher levels of job satisfaction. Their ability to adjust to changes quickly contributed to improved performance in their roles. The study highlighted that flexibility in working hours helped interns stay productive and motivated (Green et al., 2019).

Prioritizing Self-care and Mental Health

Consistent self-care practices significantly reduce stress levels and enhance resilience among individuals, particularly interns in broadcasting, who often face high-pressure environments. It reveals that those who prioritize self-care report fewer symptoms of anxiety and depression, contributing to improved overall mental health. The study emphasizes that adopting a self-care framework can

mitigate burnout, enhance job satisfaction, and improve performance in the workplace (Ayala et al., 2017).

The fourth emerging theme reveals that interns effectively overcome by prioritizing self-care and mental health, as illustrated by the experiences shared by participants 1, 2, and 3:

“...gina sulit nako akoang mga rest like akoang pag tulog gina sulit gyud na siya...” I'm really making the most of my rest, like my sleep, I'm really maximizing it. **(P1, RQ2, IGQ1)**

“...mag eat ko ug ice cream whenever na stress na kayo ko...” ...I eat ice cream whenever I'm really stressed. **(P1, RQ2, IGQ1)**

“...kana ganing imong sarili lang imohang gina storya pero maka reflect ka okay lang ba ka kay your mental health will be challenge gyud...” ..that thing where you're just talking to yourself, but you can reflect on it if you're okay, because your mental health will really be challenged. **(P2, RQ2, IGQ2)**

“...you have to survive, second is you can do to relieve your stress and also enjoy the moment...” **(P1, RQ2, IGQ1)**

Interns actively managed their mental health through practices such as regular exercise, time management, and seeking support from peers and mentors reported better overall internship experiences. These interns were more likely to remain engaged, motivated, and perform well in their tasks. The study also highlighted that mental health challenges, such as anxiety and stress, were more common among interns who neglected self-care. Organizations offering internships should actively encourage interns to take time for self-care and mental

well-being to enhance their success and long-term career prospects (Roberts and Jackson, 2020).

“...dapat kabalo gyud ka mangamusta saimohang self...”
You really need to check on yourself. **(P2, RQ2, IGQ1)**

“...mo-storya gyud ka if ever gi kalintura ba ka or unsa, of course alagaan imohang self...” ...you really need to talk if ever you have a fever or something, of course, take care of yourself. **(P3, RQ2, IGQ2)**

“Nagapahulay ko sa akong boarding house...” **(P2, RQ2, IGQ1)**

“...gikalintura gyud ko ug two days, ni-uli gyud ko ug balay ato, nagpa-ayo gyud ko...” I was really bedridden for two days, I really went home, I really got treated. **(P3, RQ2, IGQ2)**

Prioritizing self-care plays a significant role in improving mental health by reducing self-criticism and promoting emotional resilience. For broadcasting interns, practicing self-care can be an effective coping mechanism, especially when adapting to the challenges of a constantly shifting body clock. The research emphasized that taking care of one's health during periods of stress or fatigue helps interns maintain mental stability and better handle the physical demands of irregular schedules (Neff & Germer, 2017).

Incorporating self-reflection into self-care routines allows interns to better understand their emotions, pinpoint stress triggers, and create effective coping strategies. Interns were able to improve their ability to adapt to workplace challenges and maintain productivity (Keleher & Hutchinson, 2018).

Moreover, broadcasting interns effectively use self-care strategies like mindfulness and journaling as coping mechanisms for managing irregular work hours. These practices, combined with self-reflection, helped interns maintain mental health by reducing stress and enhancing emotional stability. A previous study also showed that self-care routines improved interns' adaptability to unpredictable schedules, enabling them to sustain productivity and performance (Davies & Hill, 2020).

Insights of Communication Interns Could be Helpful to Future Communication Students

Table 3 shows the themes of the insights of Communication Interns that could be helpful to future communication students. In presenting the evidence, the table illustrated sample narratives of the participants that contained statements attesting to the themes. As shown in the second column, core ideas were the main analytic description of themes.

Table 3. Insights of Communication Interns Could be Helpful to Future Communication Students.

NARRATIVES	CORE IDEAS	EMERGING THEMES
<p>“ I already know how to edit, but I really tend to forget things, so I really need to review my past learnings on how to overlay this video...” P2</p>	<p>Access past knowledge or resources</p>	<p>Importance of Foundational Knowledge</p>
<p>“ You really need to look back at your past learnings about those in writing, broadcasting, and other ethics in journalism; you should really know about that...” P2</p>		
<p>“ You should really treasure what you learned during your discussion, because those lessons are what you can truly apply...” P5</p>		
<p>“...always take note the past lessons ...” P8</p>		
<p>“ You need to learn, in a way you should already</p>		

know, it will not just stop there, so always crave for learnings..." P2

Continuous and review the lessons

" Learning is continuous; it never ends..." P2

"...review, advance your learning so that when the actual situation comes, you'll already know how it is ..." P3

"...whatever you learn in class today, don't forget it because when you get to the workplace, you'll really use it.." P5

" You really need to overcome your discomfort, you need to overcome everything because you have to do your job well as someone working in radio..." P1

Overcoming fear and Discomfort

Embracing New Experiences for Growth and Opportunity

" Don't be afraid because, if you're afraid, you won't produce any output, you won't create any information.." P2

"Being open to feedback and learning from mistakes is key to growth..." P4

" If you have any opportunities outside or inside the campus where you can get exposed to a radio setup, make sure to grab them..." P5

“ Do not be afraid to try as you may regret it later, so really experience it, grab the opportunities where you are the one trying or experiencing these things...” P2

Seek out experiences and opportunities during internships.

“Don’t be afraid to make mistakes because if you make mistakes, you’ll learn from them...” P3

“Try to be fearless and of course if you’re doubtful just ask...” P3

“When you know that it’s a bit dangerous there and all, you can talk about it...” P3

“If you have questions, so ask your supervisor or ask your colleagues, ask your classmates...” P3

Asking guidance from mentor

Importance of Collaboration and Mentorship in Broadcasting

“You really need to ask for guidance from your supervisor...” P3

“You’re not alone in your work, so you have everyone, you have friends, you have supervisors, you have instructors, and of course your classmates. Especially since we have our internship together, we know that if ever we have a problem, we have someone to talk to ...” P3

“If you are doubtful, just ask your supervisor...”P3

<p>" I gained insight into the value of teamwork and strong communication skills when collaborating with colleagues..." P4</p>	<p>Valuing of teamwork with the colleagues</p>	<p>" I also built some great relationships fellow intern and with the staff at the station. These relationships have been invaluable to me, both personally and professionally..." P5</p>	
<p>" I've learned so much from them and I'm grateful for their support and guidance." P5</p>		<p>"Always coordinate with your colleagues..." P8</p>	
<p>"Staying up to date with technological advancements..." P4</p>		<p>Technological Advancement and Proper Facilities</p>	<p>Importance of Incorporate Modern, and Advanced technological Facilities</p>
<p>"It would be even better if they had their own laboratory so that their skills could be honed right within the campus..." P5</p>		<p>"There should be a station, a TV, a small setup, something like that.." P5</p>	<p>"Create a laboratory specifically for the students, with a setup that has fully equipped tools..." P5</p>
<p>" The institution or the academic institution to provide a technological setup or an updated or</p>			

high-end radio room...” P5	Role of Proper Infrastructure
“ Needs a big radio station setup, like fully equipped...” P7	
“ We recorded it outside the school, we really need a laboratory...” P5	

Importance of Foundational Knowledge

Foundational knowledge in broadcasting serves as the essential base upon which students build their media competencies. A solid grasp of core principles such as voice modulation, scriptwriting, and audience engagement remains crucial, even as the industry continues to evolve. While broadcasting curricula have expanded to include digital media skills in response to technological advancements, it is the grounding in traditional techniques that enables students to adapt effectively to new tools and platforms. This integration of foundational and modern knowledge allows learners to navigate the shifting media landscape with both confidence and competence (Williams & Lee, 2018).

The first emerging theme concludes the importance of foundational knowledge as attested in the situation experienced by participant 2, 3, 5, and 8:

“...kabalo namn gud ko mag kanang mag edit ba pero naa gyud koy maka limtan so I really need to review my past learnings kung unsaon gani to siya na pagka sapaw, pagka over-lay ani nga video...”

...I already know how to edit, but I really tend to forget things, so I really need to review my past learnings on how to overlay this video. **(P2, RQ3, IGQ4)**

“... You really need to look back your past learnings about those your writing, broadcasting, unsa ba ang mga ethics, sa journalism, dapat kabalo gyud ka ana...” You really need to look back at your past learnings about those in writing, broadcasting, and other ethics in journalism; you should really know about that. **(P2, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“...imoha gyud i -treasure ang imohang na learn during kanang discussion ninyo, kay kana inyohang na-lesson man gud mao gyud na inyohang ma-apply...” ...you should really treasure what you learned during your discussion, because those lessons are what you can truly apply. **(P5, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“...always take note the past lessons ...” **P8, RQ3, IGQ1**

Dweck (2016) emphasized that individuals with a growth mindset believe abilities can be developed through effort and persistence. This perspective supports the value of foundational knowledge, as learners with such a mindset recognize the importance of mastering core concepts before advancing to more complex tasks. Rather than rushing toward innovation, they understand that a strong base in fundamental principles is essential for sustained learning and adaptability. This belief encourages consistent review and reinforcement of initial lessons, allowing learners to build a deeper and more resilient understanding that supports future growth.

“...you need to learn, in a way dapat kay kabalo naman ka, it well not just stop there, so always crave for learnings..” ..you need to learn, in a way you should already know, it will not just stop there, so always crave for learnings. **(P2, RQ3, IG1)**

“...ang learning man gud kay continuous na siya dili na siya mag end...” Learning is continuous; it never ends. **P2, RQ3, IGQ1**

“...mag review ka, mag advance learn ka para pag abot sa actual uhm kabalo naka na ing-anion siya...”

...review, advance your learning so that when the actual situation comes, you'll already know how it is. **(P3, RQ3, 1Q4)**

“...kung unsa imohang na learn diha karon sa klase ayaw gyud siya kalimti kay pag abot gyud sa workplace magamit gyud nimo na...”...whatever you learn in class today, don't forget it because when you get to the workplace, you'll really use it. **(P5, RQ3, IGQ4)**

This emerging theme concludes the valuable insights of communication intern that would help the future communication students. Studies showed that reviewing past learning experiences helps improve their professional development. Reflecting on their academic knowledge, interns can apply theoretical concepts more effectively to real-world tasks, boosting their performance in the field. This process helps see through between classroom learning and practical application, enhancing both their confidence and skills (Anderson et al., 2020).

Broadcasting interns can greatly benefit from reviewing and reflecting on their previous academic learning. Through revisiting their prior coursework, interns can connect theoretical knowledge with practical experience, which deepens their understanding of the broadcasting industry. This reflective process helps them recognize how the concepts they've learned apply in real-world situations, making them more adaptable and prepared for professional challenges (Harris et al., 2018).

Furthermore, broadcasting interns reflect on their previous academic learning because it helps them bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and

real-world broadcasting tasks. This reflective process enables interns to adapt more effectively to the fast-paced and ever-changing media industry. Reviewing past lessons and applying them to hands-on experiences can help interns become more confident and better equipped to handle the challenges of their internships (Lee et al., 2019).

Embracing New Experiences for Growth and Opportunity

Broadcasting provides a vital platform for professional growth, offering interns the opportunity to develop essential skills and gain practical experience in media production. By engaging in diverse tasks and real-world projects, interns embrace new experiences that broaden their competencies and deepen their understanding of the industry. Mentorship from seasoned professionals further enriches this learning process, guiding interns through challenges and helping them navigate the field more effectively. Such exposure not only enhances their technical and interpersonal skills but also increases their prospects of securing full-time positions in the competitive media landscape (Vega et al., 2020).

The second emerging theme concludes that communication interns have valuable insights that future communication students should embrace growth and opportunity in the internship industry, as attested in the situation experienced by participants 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5:

“...kailangan gyud nimo e overcome nga discomfort nimo, kailangan nimo e-overcome ang everything because you have to do your job well as a someone working in radio”...You really need to overcome your discomfort, you need to overcome everything because you have to do your job well as someone working in radio.
(P1, RQ3, IGQ1)

“Ayaw gyud kahadlok because uhm... kung mahadlok man gud ka wala kay mabuhat nga output, wala pud kay ma-create na information...” Don't be afraid because, if you're afraid, you won't produce any output, you won't create any information. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ1)**

Being open to feedback and learning from mistakes is key to growth... **(P4, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“...kung naa moy mga opportunity outside or inside the campus nga ma exposed mo sulod sa radio nga set up e-grab gyud ninyo...” ...if you have any opportunities outside or inside the campus where you can get exposed to a radio setup, make sure to grab them. **(P5 RQ3, IGQ4)**

Mistakes help build resilience and a growth mindset, both of which are crucial for adapting to the demands of the industry. Radio broadcasting is fast-paced and unpredictable, so the ability to learn from errors and stay composed under pressure is essential. Their research shows that seeking out challenges, even if it means making mistakes, helps interns develop a deeper understanding of the industry and prepares them for future roles in the field (Williams and McLeod, 2020).

“Do not be afraid to try as you may regret it later so e-experience gyud, e-grab gyud ang mga opportunity nga ikaw ang mo try or mo experience ani nga butang ...” Do not be afraid to try as you may regret it later, so really experience it, grab the opportunities where you are the one trying or experiencing these things. **(P2, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“...don't be afraid to make a mistakes kay kung naa kay mabuhat na mistakes, ma learn man na nimo...” ...don't be afraid to make mistakes because if you make mistakes, you'll learn from them. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“...try gyud inyohang self na dili mahadlok and of course kung doubtful mo just ask...” ..try to be fearless and of course if you're doubtful just ask. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ4)**

“...pag kabalo namo nga medyo dilikado didtoa and all puwede man ka mostorya..” When you know that it's a bit dangerous there and all, you can talk about it. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ 4)**

The study shows that many students who complete internships in broadcasting secure full-time jobs afterward, highlighting that internships not only offer hands-on experience but also serve as a recruitment pathway for employers. Media organizations often prefer hiring interns who have demonstrated their skills in real-world settings. This helps reduce the risks associated with hiring someone without practical experience. Proving themselves during internships, students increase their chances of securing permanent positions, making internships a crucial step toward building a broadcasting career (Zeng and Cheng, 2020).

As Carter et al. (2018) stated that internships also help students overcome the fear and uncertainty that come with entering a competitive field like broadcasting. They provide opportunities for students to grow in confidence, navigate new challenges, and learn how to seek help from mentors, colleagues, or supervisors when needed. This guidance can accelerate their development and ensure that they thrive in a professional environment, not just survive. Furthermore, students should cherish their internship experiences as they go beyond work experience by offering opportunities to build professional networks, gain industry insights, and discover personal strengths. These experiences shape future career paths, positioning students for long-term success while fostering a deeper appreciation for the broadcasting field they aim to enter (Lindsey et al., 2017).

Importance of Collaboration and Mentorship in Broadcasting

Interns who had access to strong mentorship and opportunities for collaboration with experienced professionals reported higher levels of skill acquisition and career satisfaction. Mentors provided guidance not only on technical skills but also on professional development, ethics, and navigating the media industry. Additionally, collaborative projects in real-world broadcasting settings helped interns build teamwork skills and expand their professional networks (Smith & Taylor, 2018).

The third emerging theme concludes the importance of collaboration and mentorship in broadcasting, as attested in the situation experienced by participants 3, 4, 5, and 8:

“...if mangutana ka, so ask your supervisor or ask your colleagues, ask your classmates...” ...if you have questions, so ask your supervisor or ask your colleagues, ask your classmates. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“...mag ask gyud kag guidance sa imong supervisors...” ...you really need to ask for guidance from your supervisor. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ4)**

“...wala ka nag inusara saimohang trabaho so you have everyone, you have uhm.. friends, you have supervisors, you have instructors and of course mga classmates nimo bantog gani naa tay kauban ug internship nato kay kabalo ta nga if ever naa tay problema, naa tay ma-storya...” ..you're not alone in your work, so you have everyone, you have, um, friends, you have supervisors, you have instructors, and of course your classmates. Especially since we have our internship together, we know that if ever we have a problem, we have someone to talk to. **(P3, RQ3, IGQ4)**

“...if doubtful ka, just ask lang gyud sa supervisor...” ...if you are doubtful, just ask your supervisor. (P3, RQ3, IGQ4)

The study found that interns who actively engaged with their colleagues and participated in team projects were more likely to feel confident in their abilities. The research revealed that when interns valued teamwork and worked cooperatively, they not only gained a deeper understanding of their roles within the company but also improved their interpersonal skills, which are highly sought after in the workforce (Johnson and Smith, 2019).

I gained insight into the value of teamwork and strong communication skills when collaborating with colleagues... (P4, RQ3, IGQ2)

I also built some great relationships fellow intern and with the staff at the station. These relationships have been invaluable to me, both personally and professionally... (P5,RQ3, IGQ2)

I've learned so much from them and I'm grateful for their support and guidance. (P5,RQ3, IGQ2)

Always coordinate with your colleagues... (P8, RQ3, IGQ3)

The study by Fisher and Hume (2019) shows how producers, on-air talent, and technical staff work together to create engaging content. It found that effective teamwork leads to better quality broadcasts as knowledge shared between experienced and newer team members helps improve creativity and overall output. A supportive and collaborative environment also boosts morale, motivating staff to produce their best work while reducing stress also teamwork and strong relationships within radio broadcasting teams lead to both better content and a more positive work atmosphere.

In addition, mentorship plays a key role in career development in broadcast journalism, helping individuals advance in their careers and develop important skills. It emphasizes how one-on-one mentoring in a high-pressured environment boosts job satisfaction and provides valuable guidance for navigating the challenges of the industry. This mentorship relationship not only supports professional growth but also helps build confidence and resilience in the field of broadcast journalism (Smith & White, 2017).

Importance of Incorporate Modern, and Advanced Technological Facilities

Broadcasting programs were falling behind in equipping students with the up-to-date tools necessary for success in the rapidly evolving media landscape. With advancements in digital broadcasting, podcasting, and online streaming, students without access to state-of-the-art radio labs were disadvantaged in terms of hands-on learning and skill development (Johnson & Harris, 2021).

The fourth emerging theme features the importance of incorporate modern, and advanced technological facilities, as attested in the situation experienced by participants 4, 5, and 7:

“Staying up to date with technological advancements will help future students remain competitive and innovative in the field...” Staying up to date with technological advancements will help future students remain competitive and innovative in the field. **(P4, RQ3, IGQ4)**

“Mas nindot pa kung naa silay laboratory ilaha para didto palang sulod sa campus ma hone na ilahang skills...” It would be even better if they had their own laboratory so that their skills could be honed right within the campus. **(P5, RQ3, IG4)**

“... dapat naay station, TV, gamay nga set up so ingon ato siya ...” ...there should be a station, a TV, a small setup, something like that. **(P5,RQ3, IGQ4)**

“...create ug laboratory para gyud sa mga estudyante, lahi ra gyud ug set up nga kanang full blast gyud ang mga gamit..” ...create a laboratory specifically for the students, with a setup that has fully equipped tools. **(P5, RQ3, IGQ4)**

The study found that schools with well-equipped radio rooms—featuring advanced audio equipment, high-quality microphones, soundproof studios, and up-to-date digital broadcasting tools—had students who were more successful in producing high-quality content. These students also demonstrated greater technical proficiency, as the availability of advanced technology allowed them to explore different aspects of audio production and broadcasting. The study emphasized that providing students with access to such technology not only enhanced their practical knowledge but also contributed to the development of important soft skills, such as teamwork and communication (Green and Ward, 2018).

“...the institution or the academic institution must provide a technological na mga set up or updated or high end nga radio room...” ...the institution or the academic institution to provide a technological setup or an updated or high-end radio room. **(P5, RQ3, IGQ4)**

“... kailangan gyud naay dako nga pang radio station gud na setup like kompleto gyud ang gamit...” ...needs a big radio station setup, like fully equipped. **(P7, RQ3, IGQ1)**

“... sa outside sa school pa namo gi record, kailangan naa gyud laboratory...”
We recorded it outside the school, we really need a laboratory. **(P5, RQ3, IGQ4)**

The study reveals that modern and well-equipped radio labs provide students with hands-on experience in digital audio production, automation systems, and live broadcasting tools, helping them develop the technical skills necessary for the industry. The study stresses that as the media landscape evolves, radio education must adapt by incorporating these technologies to prepare students for real-world broadcasting environments (Jones et al., 2020).

The students who had access to these advanced tools demonstrated higher levels of technical proficiency, creativity, and confidence in producing broadcast-quality content compared to those using traditional equipment. Additionally, the study found that hands-on experience with modern technologies better-prepared students for industry demands. However, challenges such as maintenance costs and the need for continuous updates were also noted (Garcia et al., 2022).

A study by Clark and Green (2018) found that adopting cutting-edge technology in radio stations not only improves operational efficiency but also benefits educational settings providing students with the skills needed to thrive in a tech-driven media landscape. Moreover, modern radio labs significantly contribute to student success in broadcasting programs. These labs, equipped with the latest technology, enable students to build crucial technical skills and foster creativity, which are vital for a career in radio broadcasting. The study also emphasizes that practical experience with advanced equipment boosts students' confidence and proficiency, preparing them more effectively for the demands of the industry (Lee & Patel, 2017).

The self-efficacy theory and Communication Accommodation Theory provide a valuable lens through which we can understand how communication interns navigate the challenges of their roles. Self-efficacy theory highlights how important it is for interns to believe in their own ability to overcome obstacles like unpredictable schedules, technical problems, and the fast-paced nature of news gathering. When interns have this confidence, it helps them tackle tasks more effectively, balance school and work, and adapt to new situations with greater ease. On the other hand, the Communication Accommodation Theory shows how essential it is for interns to adjust their communication style to build strong relationships with supervisors, colleagues, and audiences. This ability to adapt fosters better teamwork and collaboration, especially in the high-pressure environment of live broadcasts.

Aside from helping interns face immediate challenges, these theories also support their long-term growth and professional development. Self-efficacy inspires interns to apply what they have already learned while encouraging them to take on new experiences, which boosts their overall confidence. Communication Accommodation Theory reinforces the importance of collaboration and mentorship, offering the support interns need to thrive in a competitive industry. As the broadcasting world keeps evolving, these theories give interns the confidence, flexibility, and technical skills they need to succeed and grow in this ever-changing field.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND IMPLICATIONS

This chapter reviewed the research progress, outlined the main conclusions based on the findings, and offered recommendations to enhance comprehension of the study's core focus.

Summary

This study examined communication students' challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights during their radio broadcasting internships. Interns faced significant hurdles, including managing tight schedules, adapting to technical demands, and balancing academic responsibilities with irregular working hours. The fast-paced nature of radio broadcasting required them to adjust to live program schedules and early shifts, which often disrupted their routines.

News gathering was particularly challenging as it required quick adaptation to unfamiliar environments, source verification, and meeting tight deadlines. Interns often reported fatigue and being overwhelmed, as they were expected to produce multiple reports daily. The irregular hours of broadcasting, including early mornings and late-night shifts, further compounded their stress, affecting their personal lives and academic performance.

To navigate these challenges, interns employed various coping mechanisms that enhanced their adaptability and resilience. Continuous practical learning, an exploratory and adaptive approach, emerged as a vital strategy.

Interns engaged in hands-on learning through software tutorials, collaborative problem-solving, and repeated practice.

Another essential strategy was seeking mentorship and guidance in mastering broadcasting equipment and processes. Interns imitated experienced colleagues, asked questions, and participated in live sessions to become proficient with tools like soundboards and editing software. This collaborative approach not only improved technical competence but also built confidence and adaptability.

Managing irregular schedules and high-pressure settings required interns to develop effective time management strategies and prioritize self-care. Planning tasks, maintaining disciplined routines, and setting boundaries allowed them to balance overlapping responsibilities while meeting deadlines. Interns also adopted self-care practices such as mindfulness and prioritizing rest to mitigate stress and prevent burnout.

The study provided valuable insights for future interns and stakeholders. Interns emphasized the importance of revisiting foundational knowledge, such as technical editing and journalism ethics, to strengthen their practical application and confidence.

Lastly, collaboration and mentorship emerged as crucial elements of the internship experience. Interns benefited significantly from learning alongside supervisors and peers, which enhanced teamwork and problem-solving skills while building professional networks.

Conclusion

The findings of this study offered valuable insights into the application of self-efficacy theory and communication accommodation theory while illustrating how these frameworks helped explain the challenges faced by interns during their radio broadcasting internships and the strategies they used to navigate them. The study highlighted the importance of self-belief in overcoming obstacles, as emphasized by self-efficacy theory. Despite facing tight deadlines, unpredictable work hours, and technical difficulties, the interns demonstrated resilience by actively seeking mentorship, honing their skills through hands-on learning, and practicing time management and self-care. These strategies reinforced their confidence and adaptability, developing a sense of mastery that motivated them to further enhance their skills.

Additionally, the study supported the beliefs of communication accommodation theory, showing how interns adjusted their communication styles to meet the demands of the fast-paced, high-pressure broadcasting environment. In adapting their communication behaviors through collaboration, mentorship, and aligning with industry norms the interns were able to integrate smoothly into the workplace and effectively manage the challenges of live broadcasting. Their ability to adjust their communication style was essential in fostering positive relationships with colleagues and ensuring the success of live programs.

Finally, the study emphasized the critical role of foundational knowledge, mentorship, and access to resources in preparing students for the complexities of the media industry. Both theories highlighted the necessity of support systems that

built confidence, developed skills, and promoted successful adaptation to professional environments. The findings suggested that educational institutions, industry stakeholders, and mentors should collaborate to create more robust training and support structures to help students thrive in the competitive media landscape.

Implications

This study utilized qualitative research methods to explore the challenges faced, coping strategies employed, and insights gained by communication interns during their radio broadcasting internships. The findings suggested the following implications:

Communication Interns. The study offers valuable insights for communication students preparing for internships, highlighting common challenges such as time management, technical skill development, and balancing academic and professional responsibilities. By adopting strategies like continuous practical learning, seeking mentorship, and prioritizing self-care, students could strengthen their resilience and adaptability in facing these challenges.

Radio Broadcasting Industry. This study would offer valuable perspectives on the radio broadcasting sector, identifying areas for improving internship experiences and talent development. The findings might help organizations design structured, supportive programs that address skill gaps and align training with industry needs. Creating an environment that encouraged hands-on learning, mentorship, and access to updated technology could better

prepare interns for the evolving demands of radio broadcasting while cultivating a skilled future workforce.

Internship Coordinators and Supervisors. The findings emphasize the importance of understanding and addressing the unique needs of communication interns. Internship coordinators and supervisors might use these insights to provide tailored guidance, mentorship, and support. Refining program structures to balance productivity with meaningful learning opportunities could help create enriching experiences that equip students with the skills and confidence needed for professional success.

Institutions. The study provides institutions with actionable insights to enhance curricula and infrastructure. Participating practical training, fostering partnerships with broadcasting organizations, and equipping radio studios with modern technology could help bridge the gap between academic theory and professional practice. These improvements might not only better prepare students for the media industry but also strengthen the institution's reputation as a leader in communication education, producing graduates capable of meeting real-world challenges.

Educators. The study offers educators a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by communication interns, enabling them to adopt more practical, industry-aligned teaching methods. By emphasizing the application of theoretical knowledge and incorporating hands-on learning opportunities, educators could help students develop the confidence and competence needed for successful

internships, ensuring that academic programs remain relevant to industry expectations.

Future Researchers. The study set the groundwork for further research into communication and radio broadcasting internships. Future researchers might build on these findings to explore additional aspects, such as the long-term effects of internships on career growth, the role of emerging broadcasting technologies, or the experiences of interns in diverse cultural and institutional settings. Expanding the scope of research could provide broader insights into optimizing internship programs and enhancing their impact on professional development.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

LETTER TO CONDUCT STUDY FROM THE DEAN

	<p>DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105</p>	<p>president@dnscc.edu.ph dnscc.edu.ph @davnorstatercollege</p>			
<p><i>Institute of Teacher Education</i></p>					
<p>September 05, 2024</p>					
<p>ARNOLD M. DUPING, PhD Dean Institute of Teacher Education</p>					
<p>Sir:</p>					
<p>Greetings!</p>					
<p>We are Bachelor of Arts in Communication fourth-year students of Davao Del Norte State College under the Institute of Teacher Education. We are in the data collection phase in the conduct of this research relevant to our field.</p>					
<p>In this regard, we would like to ask for your permission to allow us to conduct our study about "Behind the Mic: Experiences in Radio Broadcasting Internship". The purpose of our study is to aims to explore the subjective experiences, perceptions, and interpretations of the intern communication students during their internships in radio broadcasting. This phenomenological study seeks to provide an in-depth understanding of the students' experiences, including their challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights.</p>					
<p>Your kind assistance with our request will help us effectively achieve our desired results and will be used as the basis for further studies. Moreover, the success of this study will surely gauge the development of our knowledge and practice in our field.</p>					
<p>Hoping for your wholehearted support and consideration of our fervent request.</p>					
<p>Thank you and God bless.</p>					
<p>Respectfully yours,</p>					
<p> JEME FAUNILLAN Group Leader</p>					
<p>Recommending Approval:</p>					
<p> ARNOLD M. DUPING Dean, Institute of Teacher Education</p>					
<table border="0" style="width: 100%; font-size: small;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%; vertical-align: top;"> <p>VISION A premier Higher Institution in Agri-Fisheries and Socio-cultural Development in the ASEAN Region.</p> </td> <td style="width: 33%; vertical-align: top;"> <p>MISSION DNSC strives to produce competent human resource, generate, and utilize knowledge and technology, uphold good governance and quality management system for sustainable resources and resilient communities.</p> </td> <td style="width: 33%; vertical-align: top;"> <p>CORE VALUES Excellence Integrity Innovativeness Stewardship Love of God and Country</p> </td> </tr> </table>			<p>VISION A premier Higher Institution in Agri-Fisheries and Socio-cultural Development in the ASEAN Region.</p>	<p>MISSION DNSC strives to produce competent human resource, generate, and utilize knowledge and technology, uphold good governance and quality management system for sustainable resources and resilient communities.</p>	<p>CORE VALUES Excellence Integrity Innovativeness Stewardship Love of God and Country</p>
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APPENDIX B

PROPOSAL DEFENSE MINUTES

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STATE COLLEGE**

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dmsc.edu.ph
@davnorstategcollege

Institute of Teacher Education

MINUTES OF THE OUTLINE THESIS DEFENSE
COMM 321: Communication Research / COMM415: Undergraduate Thesis

Research Title : **BEHIND THE MIC: EXPLORING THE EXPERIENCES OF DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE INTERN COMMUNICATION STUDENTS IN RADIO BROADCASTING**

Researcher(s) : **Jenie Faunillan and Jeah Hermoso**

Course/Program : **Bachelor of Arts in Communication** Semester/SY : **2023-2024**

Date/Time Defended : **JUNE 07, 2024 - 2:00 PM** Venue/Modality : **Room AB 2-4**

Comments and Suggestions	Actions Taken/Remarks	Page/Line Nos.
PRELIMINARY PAGES		
CHAPTER 1		
Background of the Study • Research Gap should be in the second paragraph and local section is irrelevant.	• Put the research gap in the second paragraph and change the local section.	• 2
Research Questions • Panel suggests number 3 question to be part of IGQ wich is "How did the DNSC Communication Program prepared system to the radio broadcast?"	•	• 3
Significance of the Study •	•	•
Scope and Limitation of the Study •	•	•
Definition of Terms •	•	•
CHAPTER 2		
Related Literature • Emphasize the other intern challenges of other institutions.	• It will based on the intern challenges of other institutions.	• 9
Related Studies •	•	•
Theoretical Lens • The one theory is irrelevant, our chair panel suggests using Communication Accommodation Theory, Constructivism, Social Identity Theory, and Constructive Alignment Theory.	• Change one theory.	• 4
CHAPTER 3		
Research Design •	• Include Inclusion/ Exclusion Criteria	• 24

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Institute of Teacher Education

Research Locale		
Research Participants/Corpora	Participants is not convincing and valid.	Participants will be the 1 st -3 rd Batch of interns in the Bachelor of Arts in Communication
Research Procedure		25
Data Collection and Analysis		
Ethical Considerations		
REFERENCES		
APPENDICES		
OTHER COMMENTS AND SUGGESTIONS		

Prepared by:

JC JUNE GALLERA
Research Adviser

Certified True and Correct:

SAIMEHEN P. ILUIS
Chairperson, Advisory Thesis Committee

Noted by:

SIGFRED F. NAVASQUEZ
Research Instructor

Advisory Thesis Committee.

Role	Name	Signature	Date
Thesis Adviser	JC JUNE GALLERA		7/12/24
Chairperson	SAIMEHEN P. ILUIS		7/17/2024
Member 1	JEVANNEL BORLIO		7/20/24
Member 2	JEZREYL JAMES CABASAG		8/13/2024

<p>VISION A premier Higher Institution in Agri-Fisheries and Socio-cultural Development in the ASEAN Region.</p>	<p>MISSION DNSC strives to produce competent human resources, generate, and utilize knowledge and technology, uphold good governance and quality management system for sustainable resources and resilient communities.</p>	<p>CORE VALUES Excellence Integrity Innovativeness Stewardship Love of God and Country</p>	
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APPENDIX C

DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE

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president@dpsc.edu.ph
dpsc.edu.ph
@davnorstacollege

Name of Institute/Office/Unit

INFORMED CONSENT FORM (ICF)

You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by Jenie Faunillan and Jeah Hermoso which is entitled "Behind the Mic: Experiences in Radio Broadcasting Internship" because you fit the inclusion criteria for informants of our study.

Your participation is completely voluntary. Please read the information below, and ask questions about anything you do not understand, before deciding whether to participate. Please take as much time as you need to read the consent form.

If you decide to participate, you will be asked to sign this form. You will be given a copy of this form.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to explore the challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of the intern communication students during their internships in radio broadcasting.

STUDY PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to participate by answering the open-ended research guide questions, which we can finish in less than 1 hour.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

You may feel discomfort during the interview because of the sensitive nature of the topic being studied. You may opt not to answer questions that make you feel any psychological or emotional distress, or you can withdraw as a participant in the study if you feel that you cannot discuss the information that is asked of you. The researchers value your participation and will place your welfare as their highest priority during the conduct of the study.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO PARTICIPANTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

This study can generate relevant information to inform best practices and strategies for supporting communication students in their radio broadcasting internships. The results, discussions, and findings from this study can provide valuable insights into the challenges, opportunities, and overall experiences of intern communication students in radio broadcasting, ultimately leading to improved internship programs and better preparation for future careers in the field. This research can contribute to the few and scanty studies on the intersection of communication education, internship experiences, and the specific demands of the radio broadcasting industry.

CONFIDENTIALITY

We will keep your records for this study confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information obtained in connection with this study will remain confidential, except if necessary, to protect your rights or welfare. This certificate means that the researcher can resist the release of information about your participation to people who are not connected with the study. When the results of the research are published or discussed in conferences, no identifiable information will be used.

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Name of Institute/Office/Unit

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

Your participation is voluntary. Your refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinu participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights, or remedies because you participate in this research study.

INVESTIGATOR'S CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact the researchers through the project leader at Davao del Norte State College, Institute of Teacher Education, BACOMM Department through mobile phone number +63-956-715-2831 or through email at hermoso.jeah@dnsc.edu.ph.

RIGHTS OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about your right as a research participant or the research in general and are unable to contact the research team, or if you want to talk to someone independent of the research team, please contact Mr. Sigfred Navasquez, the research subject teacher at 091782408051.

RESEARCH PARTICIPANT'S CONSENT

I have read the information provided above. I have been given a chance to ask questions. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. I can withdraw my consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty.

CHADREY PAUL Q. CARPE
Signature above Printed Name of Participant

09-28-2024
Date Signed

To be accomplished by the Researchers Obtaining Consent:

I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.

JENIE FAUNILLAN
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

Date Signed

TEAH HERMOSO
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

Date Signed

VISION	MISSION	CORE VALUES
Davao del Norte State College is a premier higher education institution that promotes quality education, research, innovation, and socio-economic development in the ASEAN region.	Davao del Norte State College strives to produce competent, ethical, responsible, and innovative graduates who possess the skills, knowledge, and good character to contribute to the development and quality management system for sustainable growth and well-being of the community.	Excellence Integrity Innovation Stewardship Love of God and Country

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KIMBERLY C. SULLA
Signature above Printed Name of Participant

9/21/24
Date Signed

To be accomplished by the Researchers Obtaining Consent:

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JENIE FAUNILLAN
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

9/21/24
Date Signed

JEAH HERMOSO
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

9/21/24
Date Signed

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[Handwritten Signature]
Signature above/Printed Name of Participant

9/28/24
Date Signed

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9/28/24

Date Signed

JEAH HERMOSO

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Signature above Printed Name of Participant

9/28/29
Date Signed

To be accomplished by the Researchers Obtaining Consent:

I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.

JENIE FAUNILLAN
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

9/28/29
Date Signed

JEAH HERMOSO
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

9/28/29
Date Signed

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JETHIE E. PATIÑO
Signature above Printed Name of Participant

Sept. 20, 2021
Date Signed

To be accomplished by the Researchers Obtaining Consent:

I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.

JENIE FAUNILLAN
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

Date Signed

JEAH HERMOSO
Name of Person Obtaining Consent

Date Signed

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Signature above Printed Name of Participant Date Signed

To be accomplished by the Researchers Obtaining Consent:

I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.

 _____ 9/28/29
Name of Person Obtaining Consent Date Signed

 _____ 9/28/29
Name of Person Obtaining Consent Date Signed

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APPENDIX D

APPROVED RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Interview Guide Questions on Behind the Mic: Experiences in Radio Broadcasting Internship

In this study, the researcher will focus on the Experiences in Radio Broadcasting Internship.

Given this, the study would ask;

1. What challenges do intern communication students face during radio broadcasting internships?
2. How do these intern communication students overcome the challenges they encountered during their training in radio broadcasting internships?
3. What insights of intern communication students could be helpful to future communication students?

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

INTERVIEW GUIDE QUESTIONS

PROBING QUESTIONS

1. What challenges do intern communication students face during radio broadcasting internships?

1. What challenges do you encounter during radio broadcasting internships?

1.1. What particular obstacles did you face while interning at a radio station for broadcasting?

1.2. What difficulties do you face when working together with colleagues?

2. How do these intern communication students overcome the challenges they encountered during their training in radio broadcasting internships?

2. How do you overcome the challenges you face during your radio broadcasting internships?

3. What insights of intern communication students could be helpful to future communication students?

3. 3. What valuable insights have you acquired that could benefit future communication students?

1.3. What personal challenges do you experience while working in the radio broadcasting field?

1.4. How do you face challenges when integrating technology into your work methods at a radio station?

1. How do you manage challenges while interning at a radio station?

2. How do you effectively collaborate with colleagues in radio broadcasting internships?

3. What coping strategies do you employ to address personal struggles in the radio broadcasting industry?

4. How do you address challenges when incorporating technology into your work at a radio station?

3.1. What insights did you acquire from the challenges faced during internships at a radio station?

3.2. What insights have you gained through collaborating with colleagues at a radio station?

3.3. What insights have you gained into personal struggles encountered in the radio broadcasting industry?

3.4. What insights have you gained from integrating technology into work at a radio station?

APPENDIX E

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FORMS

VALIDATION SHEET FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE

Name of Researcher: JENIE FAUNILLAN & JEAH HERMOSO
 Degree Enrolled: BACHELOR OF ARTS IN COMMUNICATION
 Title of Research: BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP
 Name of Evaluator: JANINE P. RULONA Date Evaluated: 8-22-2024

Degree of Evaluator: MAED - ENGLISH
 Position of Evaluator: INSTRUCTOR 1

Signature of Evaluator:

Rating: Number of YES marks

- () 10 Very Good () 6-7 Fair (maybe upgraded if revised)
 8-9 Good () 0-5 For Revalidation Faunillan Faunillan

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column which fits your evaluation of the item.

Items	Yes	No
Ethics:		
1. Introduction (Purpose, confidentiality, duration, way of conduct) and closing component (for additional comments) are provided.	/	
2. Informed Consent is included.	/	
Artistry:		
3. Script is included/built-in, so interviewer can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.	/	
4. Questions are appropriate to the study, enhancing the possibility of storytelling and narratives.	/	
Rigor:		
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in-depth responses; avoiding close-ended questions which are answerable by "yes" or "no".	/	
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative.	/	
7. Probe questions are provided.	/	
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority questions first opinion questions follow information questions.	/	
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	/	
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60-90 minutes not exceeding 15 open-ended items (probes excluded), for every research question, except for special cases.		/

REMARKS:

The number of questions might not be covered by 60-90 mins. Therefore, you have to observe time efficiency during the in-depth interview. Thanks! God bless!

VALIDATION SHEET FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE

Name of Researcher: JENIE FAUNILLAN & JEAH HERMOSO

Degree Enrolled: BACHELOR OF ARTS IN COMMUNICATION

Title of Research: BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP

Name of Evaluator: SAMSEL RHYS A. PAMPILON Date Evaluated: Aug 29, 2017

Degree of Evaluator: _____

Position of Evaluator: _____

Signature of Evaluator:

Rating: Number of YES marks

- () 10 Very Good () 6-7 Fair (maybe upgraded if revised)
 () 8-9 Good () 0-5 For Revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column which fits your evaluation of the item.

Items	Yes	No
Ethics:		
1. Introduction (Purpose, confidentiality, duration, way of conduct) and closing component (for additional comments) are provided.	/	/
2. Informed Consent is included.	/	/
Artistry:		
3. Script is included/built-in, so interviewer can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.	/	/
4. Questions are appropriate to the study, enhancing the possibility of storytelling and narratives.	/	/
Rigor:		
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in-depth responses; avoiding close-ended questions which are answerable by "yes" or "no".	/	/
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative.	/	/
7. Probe questions are provided.	/	/
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority questions first opinion questions follow information questions.	/	/
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	/	/
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60-90 minutes not exceeding 15 open-ended items (probes excluded), for every research question, except for special cases.	/	/

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REMARKS:

Under Eno script.

VALIDATION SHEET FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE

Name of Researcher: JENIE FAUNILLAN & JEAH HERMOSO
 Degree Enrolled: BACHELOR OF ARTS IN COMMUNICATION
 Title of Research: BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP
 Name of Evaluator: JOHN RAE V. DURAN Date Evaluated: _____
 Degree of Evaluator: M.A.P.D. - English
 Position of Evaluator: Asst. Prof. II Signature of Evaluator:

Rating: Number of YES marks

- () 10 Very Good () 6-7 Fair (maybe upgraded if revised)
 () 8-9 Good () 0-5 For Revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column which fits your evaluation of the item.

Items	Yes	No
Ethics:		
1. Introduction (Purpose, confidentiality, duration, way of conduct) and closing component (for additional comments) are provided.	9	
2. Informed Consent is included.	10	
Artistry:		
3. Script is included/built-in, so interviewer can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.	8	
4. Questions are appropriate to the study, enhancing the possibility of storytelling and narratives.	9	
Rigor:		
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in-depth responses; avoiding close-ended questions which are answerable by "yes" or "no".	10	
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative.	8	
7. Probe questions are provided.	9	
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority questions first opinion questions follow information questions.	9	
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	9	
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60-90 minutes not exceeding 15 open-ended items (probes excluded), for every research question, except for special cases.	10	

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REMARKS:

Improve the formatting of your questionnaire.

APPENDIX F

GRAMMARIAN'S CERTIFICATION

	<p>DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105</p>	<p>president@dnc.edu.ph dnc.edu.ph @davnorstatecollege</p>
<p><i>Institute of Teacher Education</i></p>		
<p>Editor's Certification</p>		
<p>This is to certify that the undergraduate thesis of JENIE O. FAUNILLAN and JEAH F. HERMOSO of Davao del Norte State College, New Visayas, Panabo City, entitled <u>BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP</u> written in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Bachelor of Arts in Communication program, has undergone proofreading in grammar from the cover page up to the last page.</p>		
<p>This certification is issued upon the request of Ms. Faunillan and Ms. Hermoso, for whatever academic purpose it may serve them, given this 3rd of February 2025, at Davao del Norte State College, Brgy. New Visayas, Panabo City.</p>		
<p> JANINE P. RULONA, MAED Proofreader/Grammarian</p>		
<p>VISION A premier higher institution in Agri-Fisheries and Socio-cultural Development in the ASEAN Region.</p>	<p>MISSION DNSC strives to produce competent human resource, generate and utilize knowledge and technology uphold good governance and quality management system for sustainable resources and resilient communities.</p>	<p>CORE VALUES Excellence Integrity Innovativeness Stewardship Love of God and Country</p>
<p></p>		

APPENDIX G

DATA ANALYST CERTIFICATION

**DAVAO DEL NORTE
STATE COLLEGE**
New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105

president@dnsc.edu.ph ✉
dnsc.edu.ph 🌐
@davnorstatecollege 📺

Institute of Teacher Education

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the results and emerging themes of the research entitled **“BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP”** prepared and submitted by **JENIE FAUNILLAN** and **JEAH HERMOSO**, in partial fulfillment for the degree of Bachelor of Arts in Communication, has been duly validated by the undersigned.

JANINE P. RULONA, MAED
 Validator

VISION

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CORE VALUES

Excellence
Integrity
Innovativeness
Stewardship
Love of God and Country

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SOCOTEC
AB

APPENDIX H

SIGNED MINUTES OF THE FINAL DEFENSE

**DAVAO DEL NORTE
STATE COLLEGE**

New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105

president@dpsc.edu.ph
dpsc.edu.ph
@davnorstatercollege

Institute of Teacher Education

MINUTES OF THE FINAL THESIS DEFENSE

COMM 321: Communication Research / COMM415: Undergraduate Thesis

Research Title : BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP

Researcher[s] : JENIE FAUNILLAN AND JEAH HERMOSO

Course/Program : Bachelor of Arts in Communication Semester/SY : SECOND

Date/Time Defended : JANUARY 06, 2025- 2-3:00 PM Venue/Modality : ACCREDITATION ROOM

Comments and Suggestions	Actions Taken/Remarks	Page/Line Nos.
PRELIMINARY PAGES and CHAPTERS 1-3		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The local literature included in the rationale does not accurately align with the focus of the study. The research gap should be placed in the final paragraph of the rationale section. The organization of the study is incomplete as it does not include Chapters 4 and 5. The paragraphs in the review of the related literature section need better connections for improved coherence. The term "intern communication students" should be replaced with "communication interns" to avoid redundancy. The review of related literature lacks a synthesis of findings and does not include any theoretical frameworks. Certain terms and phrases need to be rephrased for better clarity. Chapters 3 and onward should consistently use the past tense. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accurate local literature has been identified to align with the focus of our study. The research gap has been placed in the final paragraph of the rationale section. The organization of the study has been completed, covering Chapters 1 through 5. The paragraphs in the review of related literature have been connected to ensure better flow. "Intern communication students" has been changed to "communication interns" to avoid redundancy. A synthesis and relevant theories have been added to the concluding section of the review of related literature. Some words have been rephrased to make the text more convincing. Chapters 3 and beyond have been written in the past tense for consistency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 3 9 12 12 26 27 30 33
CHAPTER 4		
<p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certain terms in the emerging themes are not persuasive and need to be rephrased. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The words have been rephrased to create more convincing themes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 34
<p>Discussions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no synthesis regarding the application or use of the theoretical framework. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A synthesis of the application of the theoretical framework has been included in the final paragraph of the discussion section. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 88
CHAPTER 5		
<p>Summary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">
<p>Conclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The study lacks theoretical validation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theoretical validation has been incorporated into the conclusion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 91
<p>Recommendations/Implications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">

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Institute of Teacher Education

REFERENCES		
▪	▪	▪
APPENDICES		
▪	▪	▪
OTHER COMMENTS AND SUGGESTIONS		
▪	▪	▪

Prepared by:

JC JUNE C. GALLERA
Research Adviser

Certified True and Correct

SAIMEHEN P. ILUIS
Chairperson, Advisory Thesis Committee

Noted by:

SIGFRED F. NAVASQUEZ
Research Instructor

Advisory Thesis Committee.

Role	Name	Signature	Date
Thesis Adviser	JC JUNE C. GALLERA		01-14-25
Chairperson	SAIMEHEN P. ILUIS		01-28-25
Member 1	JEVANNEL BORLIO		01-28-25
Member 2	JEZREYLL JAMES CABASAG		01-20-25

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APPENDIX I

CERTIFICATE OF VALIDATION FOR CHAPTER 4 AND 5

	DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE	president@dnsc.edu.ph ✉ dnsc.edu.ph 🌐 @davnorstatecollege 📌
New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105		
<i>Institute of Teacher Education</i>		
CERTIFICATION		
<p>This is to certify that Chapters 4 and 5 of the research entitled “BEHIND THE MIC: EXPERIENCES IN RADIO BROADCASTING INTERNSHIP” prepared and submitted by JENIE FAUNILLAN and JEAH HERMOSO, in partial fulfillment for the degree of Bachelor of Arts in Communication, has been duly validated by the undersigned.</p>		
 JOHN RAE V. DURAN, MAED Validator		
VISION A premier Higher Institution in Agri-Fisheries and Socio-cultural Development in the ASEAN Region.	MISSION DNSC strives to produce competent human resource, generate, and utilize knowledge and technology, uphold good governance and quality management system for sustainable resources and resilient communities.	CORE VALUES Excellence Integrity Innovativeness Stewardship Love of God and Country

duty, where overtime is not allowed...” P2

“...You really need to wake up early because every morning, you have to visit police stations to immediately gather news or information that needs to be aired at a specific time...” P3

“....Teamwork is very important because there was a time when our output turned out poorly due to a lack of time...” P7

“...You really can't just show up, hang around, and waste your time...” P9

“...when it comes to equipment, we can hardly even handle the very large ones equipment at the station...” P1

“...the equipment, especially the technical ones at the radio broadcasting station, are not something we handle because their equipment is extremely overwhelming...” P2

“...I encountered Challenges such as mastering the technical aspects of operating broadcasting equipment and software, which

Overwhelming
Experience with the
Equipment

Technical Obstacles

initially felt
overwhelming..." (P4)

"...their equipment at the station is extremely high-tech, and we are not familiar with how to use them (equipment)..." P5

"...we never really got to try operating that rotating equipment until we arrived at the field station like DXDC, and it was very intimidating and nerve-wracking for me.] P7

"...the lack of equipment is evident, as I personally have to bring my own tools, like wired microphones and tripods, and we even borrow cameras from outside because there isn't enough equipment available..." P2

"...As pioneers, we don't have a high-grade, advanced setup for the radio..." P5

"...we didn't have proper equipment to measure the coverage area, so we couldn't determine if we could be heard in this barangay or in Caganguhan—we were just talking there without knowing..." P6

"...technology was really challenging for me; I

Limited Access to Advanced Technology

struggled a lot because I wasn't knowledgeable enough because the equipment was insufficient..." P7

"...you need to write news and submit it immediately because while patrolling, the radio in the vehicle will ask for information based on what you gathered during the interview..." P1

Managing News
Deadlines in unfamiliar
Environments

**Difficulty in News
Gathering**

"...during our radio broadcasting internship, there was no place conducive for us interns to prepare and write news, so gathering news was really difficult.." P2

"...gathering news isn't easy during press conferences because sometimes we are sent by Ma'am to specific agencies or hotels, but since we aren't familiar with the locations, we end up getting lost..." P3

"...we are not very familiar with Davao, and we are sent to press conferences in unfamiliar places. Our news head always tells us, 'You must submit your news this time,' even though we aren't familiar with the area..." P5

“...we go to different police stations, and once we get the blotter entry, we have to immediately create our news item to report, and we only have a few minutes to gather the necessary information...” P8

“...every day, we had to create five news articles plus an additional feature article, and it was very exhausting...” P2

Self-Reliant News
Content Development

“...we had to look for news content ourselves at that time, and we used scripts that we invented on our own because we were the first batch. We tried to find a proper format, but at that time, there was none available...” P5

“...interviewing was challenging because we would meet different kinds of people, so the content had to be varied to gather accurate news...” P7

“...we were the ones reporting the news, and designing everything doing all of that ourselves...” P9

“...There are times when you are assigned to work very late, or your shift

<p>gets extended into the night due to heavy demands..." P1</p>	<p>Irregular and Extended Work Hours</p>	<p>Obstacles Due to Inconsistent Working Hours</p>
<p>"...I worked for 15 hours, went home at 10 PM, and had to return at 4 AM the next morning..." P1</p>		
<p>"...the first week of your internship, you are assigned to the AM shift, and then the next week you switch to the PM shift, so it's very difficult to adjust..." P6</p>		
<p>"...the radio shifts are divided into AM and PM schedules, with AM from 4 AM to 12 noon and PM from 1 PM to 8 PM, making adjustments and shift changes very challenging..." P8</p>		
<p>"...During scheduling at that time, we couldn't all fit in one office because there were too many of us..." P5</p>	<p>Complexity of Scheduling and Limited Resources in Field Work</p>	
<p>"...we were split into smaller groups, so on some days only three of us would be present, and the next day, three again. This limited the time we had for hands-on learning or our assigned schedules..." P6</p>		
<p>"...our OJT focused on fieldwork, so we were on a shifting schedule. One day we stayed at the</p>		

station, and the next day we went out into the field...” P7

“...we worked manually because there was no exact assigned schedule...” P9

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

NARRATIVES	CORE IDEAS	EMERGING THEMES
<p>“...learning through observations as well as learning on applying what you observe throughout the people working in the radio station...”P1</p> <p>“...I already know how to do the basics there, doesn't mean to stay at that level, so through continuous learning...” P2</p> <p>“...I focused on continuous learning and practice...”P4</p> <p>“...Through exploration because we are the first batch..” P5</p> <p>“...”Even though the work in media, especially in radio, is very tiring and challenging, I still continue and learn every time from them...” P8</p> <p>“...By searching for what can possibly be done in</p>	<p>Continuous Practical Learning</p>	<p>Embracing learning and applying skills through observing and persevering</p>

<p>TV, Print, and Radio..." P2</p>	<p>Adaptive Resilience and Technological Mastery</p>	<p>"...I expected the unexpected, there were times when I'd go, 'Ahh okay, I'm ready to face this, I can do this..." P2</p>
<p>"...In the media industry, you really need to ask them because we need information; we need the kind of information that is also needed by the people..." P3</p>		<p>"...When it comes to technology, you really need to learn it as well..." P8</p>
<p>"...If you have difficulties with the equipment, you are encouraged to really ask for guidance from your supervisors or your colleagues..." P1</p>		
<p>"...I can't help but keep asking questions, even if it feels a bit awkward, because by asking, you have someone to guide you in case you make a mistake..." P3</p>	<p>Asking for Guidance</p>	<p>Seeking Guidance in Familiarizing Equipments and Facilities</p>
<p>"...I spent extra time familiarizing myself with the equipment and broadcast software, seeking help from more experienced colleagues when needed..." P4</p>		
<hr/>		

“...with technology, the only way to overcome challenges is to try, even if you don’t know how...”

P5

Proactivity and Initiative
in Learning

“...you really need to have the ability to use the technology related to the media even the basic...”

P2

“...I learned to stay calm under pressure and trust my training, which helped me make quick and confident decisions...”

P4

“...You really need to learn, as I mentioned earlier, about Adobe Photoshop and Adobe Premiere...” P8

“...Don’t hesitate to ask, especially with your supervisors, because the instructions need to be completely clear before you go out into the field...” P9

“...in terms of personal adjustments, I just woke up early, but honestly, it’s really unavoidable to be late...” P5

Adjusting routines

**Developing Time
Consistency**

“...just wake up early...”
P5

“ Time management and scheduling are really important...” P6

<p>“... I just find time, because sometimes, I struggle with my schedule, but I can still adjust...” P7</p>	<p>Adapting to changing work schedules</p>	
<p>“...planning time is really important so that work doesn't overlap...” P7</p>		
<p>“...waking up at 3 AM, of course, it really requires discipline and it changes your lifestyle...” P9</p>		

<p>“ I'm really making the most of my rest, like my sleep, I'm really maximizing it...” P1</p>	<p>Prioritizing Rest and Physical Care for Mental Well-being</p>	<p>Prioritizing Self-care and Mental Health</p>	
<p>“ I eat ice cream whenever I'm really stressed...” P1</p>			
<p>“...that thing where you're just talking to yourself, but you can reflect on it if you're okay, because your mental health will really be challenged...” P2</p>			

<p>“...you really need to talk if ever you have a fever or something, of course, take care of yourself...” P3</p>		
<p>“...you have to survive, second is you can do to relieve your stress and also enjoy the moment...” P1</p>	<p>Recognizing the Importance of Mental Health and Self-care</p>	
<p>“...you really need to check on yourself...” P2</p>		

" I am resting at my boarding house..." P2

" I have a fever for two days, I really went home, I really got treated..." P3

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

NARRATIVES	CORE IDEAS	EMERGING THEMES
<p>" I already know how to edit, but I really tend to forget things, so I really need to review my past learnings on how to overlay this video..." P2</p>	<p>Access past knowledge or resources</p>	<p>Importance of Foundational Knowledge</p>
<p>" You really need to look back at your past learnings about those in writing, broadcasting, and other ethics in journalism; you should really know about that..." P2</p>		
<p>" You should really treasure what you learned during your discussion, because those lessons are what you can truly apply..." P5</p>		
<p>"...always take note the past lessons ..." P8</p>		
<p>" You need to learn, in a way you should already know, it will not just stop there, so always crave for learnings..." P2</p>	<p>Continuous and review the lessons</p>	
<p>" Learning is continuous; it never ends..." P2</p>		

“...review, advance your learning so that when the actual situation comes, you'll already know how it is ...” P3

“...whatever you learn in class today, don't forget it because when you get to the workplace, you'll really use it..” P5

“ You really need to overcome your discomfort, you need to overcome everything because you have to do your job well as someone working in radio...” P1

Overcoming fear and Discomfort

Embracing New Experiences for Growth and Opportunity

“ Don't be afraid because, if you're afraid, you won't produce any output, you won't create any information..” P2

“Being open to feedback and learning from mistakes is key to growth...” P4

“ If you have any opportunities outside or inside the campus where you can get exposed to a radio setup, make sure to grab them...” P5

“ Do not be afraid to try as you may regret it later, so really experience it, grab the opportunities where you are the one trying or experiencing these things...” P2

Seek out experiences and opportunities during internships.

“Don’t be afraid to make mistakes because if you make mistakes, you’ll learn from them...” P3

“Try to be fearless and of course if you’re doubtful just ask...” P3

“When you know that it’s a bit dangerous there and all, you can talk about it...” P3

“If you have questions, so ask your supervisor or ask your colleagues, ask your classmates...” P3

Asking guidance from
mentor

**Importance of
Collaboration and
Mentorship in
Broadcasting**

“You really need to ask for guidance from your supervisor...” P3

“You’re not alone in your work, so you have everyone, you have friends, you have supervisors, you have instructors, and of course your classmates. Especially since we have our internship together, we know that if ever we have a problem, we have someone to talk to ...” P3

“If you are doubtful, just ask your supervisor...”P3

“ I gained insight into the value of teamwork and strong communication skills when collaborating with colleagues...” P4

Valuing of teamwork with
the colleagues

" I also built some great relationships fellow intern and with the staff at the station. These relationships have been invaluable to me, both personally and professionally..." P5

" I've learned so much from them and I'm grateful for their support and guidance." P5

"Always coordinate with your colleagues..." P8

"Staying up to date with technological advancements..." P4

Technological
Advancement and Proper
Facilities

**Importance of
Incorporate Modern, and
Advanced technological
Facilities**

"It would be even better if they had their own laboratory so that their skills could be honed right within the campus..." P5

"There should be a station, a TV, a small setup, something like that.." P5

"Create a laboratory specifically for the students, with a setup that has fully equipped tools..." P5

" The institution or the academic institution to provide a technological setup or an updated or high-end radio room..." P5

Role of Proper
Infrastructure

" Needs a big radio station setup, like fully equipped..." P7

“ We recorded it outside the school, we really need a laboratory...” P5

APPENDIX K

INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPTION AND TRANSLATION

PARTICIPANT	TRANSCRIPTION	TRANSLATION
	RQ 1. What challenges do intern communication students face during radio broadcasting internships?	
	IGQ1. What challenges do you encounter during radio broadcasting internships?	
PARTICIPANT 1	During my internship, we have 3 rotation and radiobroadcast is my last rotation so basically I exerted more, my energy most of my energy in the first rotations but still I had energy to spare for my last rotation so its like nakapoy nako sa akoang first two months and sa akong last rotation sa radio murag gamay nalang ang akong energy gani so mao na siya ang isa sa mga obstacles didtoa pero part man gihapon siya sa internships so kailangan jud nimo mang gahot gihapon and siguro ang isa pud sa mga obstacles sa radio station for broadcasting na internship is just sayo kayo sila mag start ug ano, sayo kayo mag start ang trabaho like alas kwatro palang dapat naa naka didto-a sa station and bawal ka malate kay everything is on air so whenever na mag live na on air na dapat everything is settled na everything is ready na so, time management pd ang isa sa mga obstacles didto aside from that ano pd siya naa poy mga	During my internship, we had three rotations. Radio broadcasting was my last rotation, so I put in more effort and used most of my energy during the first rotations. However, I still had some energy left for the final rotation. I was tired after the first two months, and my energy was lower during the radio broadcasting rotation. This was one of the challenges I faced, but it was still part of the internship experience, so I had to push through. Another obstacle I faced at the radio station was the early start times. They begin work very early, around 4 AM. You have to be at the station by then, and being late is not an option because everything is live on air. When they go live, everything needs to be set up and ready, so time management is crucial. Aside from that, there were times when I was assigned late-night shifts or had to work

	times na ma assign ka na gabii na kaayo or ma extend inyong trabaho nga maabtan mo ug gabii kay na.	overtime, which sometimes extended into the night.	
PARTICIPANT 2	For me ang isa sa mga obstacle na akoang na agi-an during sa internship sa radio broadcasting specifically sa RMN kay it is been a total adjustment like its seems like nag tuyok ang world 360 degrees kay from 8-5PM na duty na bawal ang over time , ni abot sa panahon na kato like 4 AM sayo kaayo naa namoy schedule nga mag report sa office or sa station tapos it seems like you really need to manage your time kay dili gyud siya pwede na kana ganing igo lang ka mosulod didtoa na mag tambay unya mag patay-patay ra saimong oras, kay sa akoang experience isa ka adlaw dapat mag create dapat mi ug five ka news articles unya plus additional pa jud na feature article so kapoy kaayo siya actually panahon sa radiobroadcasting namo na internship and wla kaayo siyay, kana ganing wala kaayo siyay place na pwede namo buhatan na very conducive for us unta na intern tapos, at the same time isa pud na challenges is ang mga equipments, like naa juy part na which is the technical part didtoa sa radiobroadcasting na station no na dili namo siya gina tarog it is because grabe ang kana ganing grabe ka overwhelming ang ilahang equipment.	I completely agree with participant 1. We had similar experiences, but he was on his third rotation in radio broadcasting, while I was in the middle of my rotations. I went from TV to radio, and my final rotation will be in print media. One of the biggest challenges I faced during my radio broadcasting internship, specifically at RMN, was the complete adjustment required. It felt like the world turned 360 degrees! I went from a typical 8 AM to 5 PM work schedule with no overtime to a situation where I had to be at the station by 4 AM for early morning reporting. Time management became crucial because you couldn't just show up, hang around, and waste time. In my experience, we had to create five news articles per day, plus an additional feature article. It was very demanding, and the radio broadcasting internship lacked a dedicated space that was conducive for us interns to work. Another challenge was the equipment. The technical aspects of the radio broadcasting station were overwhelming.	
PARTICIPANT 3	Dili lalim na mag magmata ka ug sayo then pagka madugay	It's not easy to wake up early, come home late, and then	

	<p>ka ug uli then mata na pud kag sayo for sunod na duty, for 4-12 AM then sa hapon kay 1-9, sa ang amoa man gud to before kay is 1 week 4 to 12 tapos isa napud ka week is 1-9 so dili siya kaya sa lawas namo at some point kay nag adjust mi and then dili siya lalim pud na week kay ang environment na inyong gi-adtuan is kanang dili mo familiar, daghan mi nangasaag actually sa Davao , baguhan gyud mi didtoa, didtoa mi nagka problema sa radio broadcasting ka na ano na field kay need gyud nimo mosayo ug nimo ug mata.</p>	<p>wake up early again for the next shift. We had a schedule where we worked 4 AM to 12 PM for one week, and then 1 PM to 9 PM the next week. It was tough on our bodies, but we eventually adjusted. It was also difficult because the work environments were unfamiliar. We were actually all new to Davao, so we had a lot of challenges adjusting, especially in the radio broadcasting field. You have to wake up very early because you need to get news or information from police stations and other sources to be able to air it at a specific time.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 4	<p>During radio broadcasting internship, I encountered challenges such as mastering the technical aspects of operating broadcasting equipment and software, which initially felt overwhelming. Additionally, adjusting to the fast-paced nature of the industry and balancing multiple responsibilities, such as script preparation, news production, editing, and on-air presentation, added to the difficulty.</p>	<p>During radio broadcasting internship, I encountered challenges such as mastering the technical aspects of operating broadcasting equipment and software, which initially felt overwhelming. Additionally, adjusting to the fast-paced nature of the industry and balancing multiple responsibilities, such as script preparation, news production, editing, and on-air presentation, added to the difficulty.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 5	<p>Sa personal nga challenge is Davao base man gud ang tanan and amoang internship na area so sa radio, sa DXDC mi sa RMN Davao unya ako personally ng ana struggle nako is dili man gud ko taga Davao kay taga Panabo man gyud ko so I have to uhm to leave sa Davao, kanang mag boarding</p>	<p>My personal challenge was that everything was based in Davao, and that was where our internship was. We were at DXDC, at RMN Davao. My personal struggle was that I'm not from Davao, I'm from Panabo, so I had to leave and find a place to stay. I didn't stay in a boarding house, I lived</p>	

	<p>house pero wala ko nag boarding house, nag puyo ko sa akoang angkol nga layo siya sa centro ang akoang gipuy-an so ang radio man gud kay 24 hours man naga air na sila kung dili na sila mo air, kuan lang siguro kadlwaon lang sa ala una hantod alas tres but four hantod gabii na naa na silay mga blocking time ana, blocking na mga presentation so we have to in at exactly earlier at 6 AM so unya sa Davao dili siya duol so mao to siya ang akoang personal struggle na challenge didto.</p>	<p>with my uncle, but it was far from the city center. The radio station is on air 24 hours a day, except maybe for a short break from 1 AM to 3 AM. But from 4 PM to late at night, they have blocking times for presentations. So, we had to be there early, at 6 AM. And in Davao, it's not easy to get around. That was my personal struggle</p>	
PARTICIPANT 6	<p>As a pioneering batch ug communication students, that time Kami gyud ang nag ahcraft, pag established sa North Radio that time ang struggle lang namo that time was the resources kay yes we know theoretically unsaon pag buhat pero wala mi kanang wala mi enough fund nga kanang para e put up ang mismong radio station.</p>	<p>As a pioneering batch of communication students, that time, we were the ones who crafted it when North Radio was established the only struggle we had at that time was the resources because yes, we knew theoretically how to do it but we didn't have enough funds to set up the actual radio station.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 7	<p>Daghan jud kog na encounter sa subjects namo before sa 2nd year naa mi radio broad pero online man gud sya so wala jud mi ka try unsaon pag operate atong mga tuyok tuyok(equipment) didto sa kuan so mag alig rami atong mga classmate namo nga hawd jud mo operate unya pag abot namo didtoa sa kuan na jud field najud like sa DXDC najud na kuratan og nakulbaan ko kay Ginoo ko hala basin pa operaton kog kuan ani kanang radio kanang mga ana ana ba pa operaton ko ani unsaon ko</p>	<p>I encountered a lot in our subjects before in the 2nd year. We had a radio broadcast, but it was online, so we never really got to try operating the equipment there. We relied on our classmates who were really good at operating. When we finally got to the field, like at DXDC, I was shocked and scared because I thought, "Oh my God, what if they make me operate the radio? What if they think, ' what are these DNSC students doing, they're so incapable?"</p>	

	<p>mani basin ilang isip ba bay hala unsa maning taga DNSC uy.</p>		
PARTICIPANT 8	<p>Sa Radio station of course fast pacing man gyud ang radio especially sa paghatod sa balita so dapat sa radio mauna dapat ang balita nila compare nimo sa TV so kung kinahanglan paspas pod ka dapat magkuha og mga informations so kung paspas mo kuha og information for example kadtong during atong akong internship na every 4 AM magkuha mo og ahm letter entry so mag-adto mo sa different police station so kinahanglan inig kuha nimo sa blotter entry mag himo pod ka dayon sa imohang news item para ibalita so mga I think pila lang ka minutes ang ihatag sa imoha so dapat mag study gyud pod ka dapat daan so ang pinaka importante is study gyud and daghan kaayu ka ug adjustments especially sa radio and sa format unsaon nila paghatod sa balita kay every agency man gud or session lahi-lahi na sila og format so kailangan mag study gyud ka ahead of time palang.</p>	<p>In radio station of course its fast pacing to deliver a news, it's a must in radio that the news should come first compared in Television you need to be fast to get information for example during my internship, every 4 am you need to get letter entry in different police station when you get the blotter entry you will immediately create a news item to do a news I think they will give you a few minutes so you need to study in advance. The most important is to study and you have many adjustments especially in radio and the format on how to deliver the news, in every agency or session they have different format so you need to study ahead of time.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 9	<p>Challenges first siguro graphic materials like intern ka sa broadcasting the good thing ahm in Davao because I witnessed man gud internship hearing man gud nila mas strict sila sa national compared to the provinces na mga intern mas ahm mas open ba so during our time gina allow mi to mag field work, mag field research ahm graphic materials in context so ahm like mga na banggaan on</p>	<p>The first challenge, maybe graphic materials like when you're an intern in broadcasting. The good thing in Davao, because I witnessed the internship, they are stricter at the national level compared to the provinces where interns are more open. So during our time, we were allowed to do field work, field research, and work with graphic materials in context. For example, like</p>	

	<p>early morning mao na imong sulaton like news mao na imong makita so especially if first someone na kanang medyo malipong gud pag makita ka og dugo-dugo something ana like grieving families kana isa na siya sa mga challenges na ahm kaharapon to ano ba to report a news with graphic contents and materials na inyong makita personally that eventually ahm maano naman ahm ma overcome naman, siguro mas tough man gud ang industry so mas ma tough pod ka very ana lang.</p>	<p>accidents in the early morning, that's what you would write about in the news, that's what you would see. Especially if you're a first-timer and you get a bit dizzy seeing blood or something like that, like grieving families. That's one of the challenges, to report news with graphic contents and materials that you personally see. Eventually, you can overcome it. The industry is tough, so you have to be tough too, just like that.</p>	
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PARTICIPANT	TRANSCRIPTION	TRANSLATION	
RQ2. How do these intern communication students overcome the challenges they encountered during their training in radio broadcasting internships?			
IGQ2: How do you overcome the challenges you face during your radio broadcasting internships?			
PARTICIPANT 1	<p>Kailangan gyud nimo mag survive tapos on that stage of my life naga apas ka both sa among pag graduate and sa intership na mahuman nimo siya na ma (what we called that) accomplish nimo siya excellently and mahatagan nimo siya ug justice ang imong own rotations sa imong intership even maskin imong last rotations na internships so what I did was gina sulit</p>	<p>You really need to survive that stage of life. You're juggling graduation and finishing your internship, trying to accomplish it excellently and do justice to your own rotations, even during your final rotations. What I did was sacrifice my rest, like sleep. I would only sleep for six hours or even reduce that by two hours sometimes. I would also</p>	

	<p>nako akoang mga rest like akoang pag tulog gina sulit gyud na siya maskin 6 hours lang na siya or mag decrease of two hours also sometimes mag eat ko ug ice cream whenever na stress na kayo.</p>	<p>eat ice cream whenever I was stressed.</p>	
<p>PARTICIPANT 2</p>	<p>I think nga naka help sa akona no to overcome the challenges in radiobroadcasting na mga moments nga pina ka una gyud kay pressuring myself so gi pressure gyud nako ug taman ang akoang self na kana ganing imohang notes kay puno na ug dapat mo graduate ka so by having that kay syempre ganahan man kaayo ko mag sige ug notes, mag sige ug journal so pressure nako ug taman akoang sarili na kana ganing dapat maka graduate ka, dapat ma prove nimo nga maka human ka sa internship kay actually it has been 3 months man gud ang internship so murag gani ug maka ano tapos layo pa gyud ka saimong family, maka question gyud ka kung Makaya ba so gi pressure nako akoang self na dapat mahuman nimo ang internship nimo nga kana ganing walay labad dili ikaw ang kana ganing I mean maka cope gyud ka sa mga expectations at the same time maka human pud ka sa thesis while naa ko sa akoang boarding house didto gyud nako kana ganing gi kulong nako akoang self nga naga buhat every time na naa sad</p>	<p>I think that helped me overcome the challenges of radio broadcasting, especially in those early, pressuring moments. I pressured myself a lot, filling my notes with reminders to graduate. I was really into taking notes and journaling, so I pressured myself to graduate and prove that I could finish the internship. It was a three-month internship, and I was far away from my family, so I questioned if I could handle it. I pressured myself to finish the internship without any problems, to meet expectations and complete my thesis. I locked myself in my boarding house and worked constantly, taking breaks to relax by opening my laptop.</p>	

	pahulay , naga relax ko thru opening my laptop so ingon ana.		
PARTICIPANT 3	Dili gyud mawala sa akua ang sige ug pangutana bahala ug ulaw siya basta mangutana gyud kay para naa kay incase mamali atleast nay nag guide saimo, so mao to siya para sa pag overcome kung unsaon siya pag pag gamit ana, ang imo lang gyud kauban ana or ang imohang kakampi is ang imohang self, kailangan gyud nimo na pataason pa gyud nimo imong confidence, dapat magpa baga gyud ka ug nawong, mo-atubang gyud ka sa imong supervisors to act kay wala may mali sa pag pangutana isa na siya e-Overcome.	I always ask questions, even if I'm a little embarrassed. I just ask because if I make a mistake, at least I have someone to guide me. That's how I overcome the challenge of using technology. Your only ally is yourself. You need to boost your confidence, be bold, and face your supervisors because there's nothing wrong with asking questions. That's one way to overcome all those challenges.	
PARTICIPANT 4	To overcome the challenges I faced during my radio broadcasting internships, I focused on continuous learning and practice. I spent extra time familiarizing myself with the equipment and broadcast software, seeking help from more experienced colleagues when needed. I also developed time management skills, prioritizing tasks to ensure I met deadlines without feeling overwhelmed. Whenever we are having a receded broadcasts, I learned to stay calm under pressure and trust my training, which helped me make quick and confident decisions.	To overcome the challenges I faced during my radio broadcasting internships, I focused on continuous learning and practice. I spent extra time familiarizing myself with the equipment and broadcast software, seeking help from more experienced colleagues when needed. I also developed time management skills, prioritizing tasks to ensure I met deadlines without feeling overwhelmed. Whenever we are having a receded broadcasts, I learned to stay calm under pressure and trust my training, which helped me make quick and confident decisions.	
PARTICIPANT 5	The only way para maka pa overcome is to try, yes bisan	The only way to overcome it was to try. You can't go to work	

	<p>wala ka kabalo unya pag abot man gud nimo sa work place, dili pud ka pwede mo ingon nga “maam wala ko kabalo” dili pud ka pwede mo ingon ana didto, imo gyud siyang e-try so ang nahitabo, ang gibuhat namo even the fact nga wala mi kanang high end na mga set up sa sulod sa campus, among gibuhat nag try lang gyud mi so we request the head sa amoang news room na “maam okay lang ba na mag learn mi ani na mga butang” ana then at the end of the day naka learn ra pud mi.</p>	<p>and say, "Ma'am, I don't know how to do this." You have to try. So, what we did, even though we didn't have high-end equipment on campus, we just tried. We asked our newsroom head, "Ma'am, can we learn how to use this equipment?" And at the end of the day, we learned how to use the software and equipment there.</p>
PARTICIPANT 6	<p>Para ma cope up lang gyud namo no, kung unsa among dapat mahibal-an kay kanang to really understand each other.</p>	<p>In terms of colleagues, that time we really needed to cope with what we had to learn, to really understand each other.</p>
PARTICIPANT 7	<p>Gi pugos nalang jud nako kay ngano? Layo naman gud di ko puyde mo undang siguro kay ano lang dedicated lang guro kay busy man gud jud to like oh like huna huna namo naa pami thesis naa pami ojt, pag uli sa boarding house mag thesis pa nya kasab-an paka sa imung mga panel mga ing ana so ang akua kay siguro dedication lang jud gang mao na overcome nako.</p>	<p>I just forced myself because it was too far along, and I couldn't stop. Maybe it was just dedication because we were really busy, like thinking about our thesis and OJT. When we got back to the boarding house, we still had to work on our thesis, and we would get scolded by our panels. So for me, it was probably just dedication.</p>
PARTICIPANT 8	<p>Kailangan imo ng studyhan gyud before palang ka mo intern dapat kabalo naka unsay kailangan nimo ma tun-an and then don't hesitate to ask kay especially sa imong mga supervisors kay dapat klaro gyud daan ang instruction before ka mo go sa</p>	<p>You should already know what you need to learn. And don't hesitate to ask, especially your supervisors, because the instructions should be clear before you go to the field. You need to be proactive and quick because you will be assigned to the radio.</p>

	field para kabalo ka daan and go lang gyud pirme dapat active gyud ka dapat paspas gyud imong lihok kay sa radio man ka na-assign		
PARTICIPANT 9	Syempre discipline gyud change gyud siya og lifestyle because in ano man gud in radio like one week for now 3 am or 4 am mo and then next week pang evening mo so imagine ang body clock paiba-iba diba so ano like discipline gyud siya kay diba like after work diba naa pa tay for leisure time naa pa tay gusto lakawon ana but you know ma lessen gyud siya once nakay response once like naa nakay work because its a job dili lang siya murag intern-intern expect to be care kay naa kay assignment so more in discipline ang nagapa overcome sa akong mga challenges.	So it's really about discipline because, after work, we still have leisure time, we still have things we want to do, but you know, it lessens once you have responsibilities, once you have work. Because it's a job, not just an internship where you can just relax; you have assignments. So it's really discipline that helps me overcome my challenges.	

PARTICIPANT	TRANSCRIPTION	TRANSLATION	
RQ3. What insights of intern communication students could be helpful to future communication students?			
IGQ3: What valuable insights have you acquired that could benefit future communication students?			
PARTICIPANT 1	I have acquired lots of valuable insights during my internship in the radiobroadcasting station, first is doing your best even you're not in a very	I gained a lot of valuable insights during my radio broadcasting internship. First, you have to do your best even if you're not in a very comfortable working space. Radio stations aren't always	

	<p>comfortable working space so in a radio station it is not prestitious and also there are times daghan na pud ug interns so wala na kay kabutangan saimong sarili bu you have to meet the deadlines, you have to do your task, and you have to do your best.</p>	<p>glamorous, and there are often a lot of interns, so you might not have your own space. But you still have to meet deadlines, complete your tasks, and do your best.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 2	<p>I think pina una is you really need to prepare, just like what I have said na you need to know or you need to expect the unexpected. Ang ika duha kay review, so you really need to look back your past learnings about those your writing, broadcasting, unsa bang mga ethics, sa journalism, dapat kabalo gyud ka ana ereview gyud na kay for sure pag abot nimo didtoa matingala nalang sila na nga "wala diay mo gitudloan ug ingon ani na pagka sulat, nganong ang imohang of way of writing man kay dili man siya news?" ingon ana so ereview gyud nimo na na mga learnings.</p>	<p>I think the first thing is to prepare. Like I said, you need to expect the unexpected. The second is to review. You need to look back at your past learnings about writing, broadcasting, journalistic ethics. You need to know that stuff and review it because you might be surprised when you get there and they say, "You weren't taught how to write like this? Why is your writing style not news-worthy?" So, review those learnings.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 3	<p>Ang valuable na mga insights gyud nako na na acquire during sa internship is isa gyud tong giingon nila na ayaw gyud kahadlok because uhm kung mahadlok man gud ka wala kay mabuhat nga output, wala pud kay ma-create na information, so don't be afraid to make a mistakes kay kung naa kay mabuhat na mistakes, ma learn man na nimo, then kung doubtful ka saimong ginabuhat like for example dili ka</p>	<p>One of the most valuable insights I gained during my internship was something they always said: don't be afraid. If you're afraid, you won't produce anything, you won't create any information. Don't be afraid to make mistakes because you learn from them. If you're unsure about something, like you're not sure how to do something, don't hesitate to ask. Ask your supervisor, ask your colleagues, ask your classmates.</p>	

	<p>sure and all so wala gyud mawala saimoha if mangutana ka, so ask your supervisor or ask your colleagues, ask your classmates</p>		
PARTICIPANT 4	<p>The valuable insights I acquired that could benefit future communication students include the importance of adaptability and resilience in the broadcasting industry. Being open to feedback and learning from mistakes is key to growth. Additionally, I gained insight into the value of teamwork and strong communication skills when collaborating with colleagues. Understanding the technical side of broadcasting, combined with creativity, is essential for producing high-quality content. Lastly, staying up to date with technological advancements will help future students remain competitive and innovative in the field.</p>	<p>The valuable insights I acquired that could benefit future communication students include the importance of adaptability and resilience in the broadcasting industry. Being open to feedback and learning from mistakes is key to growth. Additionally, I gained insight into the value of teamwork and strong communication skills when collaborating with colleagues. Understanding the technical side of broadcasting, combined with creativity, is essential for producing high-quality content. Lastly, staying up to date with technological advancements will help future students remain competitive and innovative in the field.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 5	<p>Una is imoha gyud e-treasure ang imohang na learn during kanang discussion Ninyo, kay kana inyohang na lesson man gud mao gyud na inyohang bala when it comes to application.</p>	<p>First, treasure what you learn during your discussions because those lessons are what you'll use when you apply it.</p>	
PARTICIPANT 6	<p>We need to empty our cup in terms of mag adto rata sa atoang ahm...sa atoang agency kuntahay if ever mo trabaho nata or mo sulod nata as intern it's because dili sa tanang panahon kabalo ka sa tanang butang</p>	<p>We need to empty our cup in terms of going to our agency. If ever we work or enter as interns, it's because not all the time do you know everything.</p>	

PARTICIPANT 7	Give nalang jud ninyo inyung best jud, kung naa namo didtoa sa field mag ojt namo, e give jud ninyo inyung best unsay makaya ninyo kung siguro kung ma ulaw mo siguro bawal jud mag ulaw ulaw guro didtoa pag pakitang gilang jud mo didto dapat dedicated jud pud mo ug work ano lang salig jud mo sa inyung sarili.	When you are there, give your best because they will notice you. when you are there in the field doing your OJT, give your best in whatever you can. If you feel shy, it's really not allowed to be shy there. Show your skills, you should be dedicated to your work. Just trust yourself.
PARTICIPANT 8	Always take notes especially your supervisors instructions dapat before ka mo go sa field kay naa man gyud nay instruction ang imohang supervisor aside from taking notes mag ready pod ka sa imohang cellphone kung puwede duha ka cellphone para ang isa pag take og picture ang isa pang record gyud sa audio kay incase dili nimo ma-take note tanan na giingon tungod pod sa kapaspas pod of course sa ilahang gipang ingon sa mga guest so dapat naa pod kay audio or naka record na audio na imong balikan pag-abot sa station or sa sakyanan maghimo ka og news item and always coordinate with your colleagues	Always take notes, especially your supervisor's instructions, before you go to the field because your supervisor will definitely have instructions for you. aside from taking notes, you should also be ready with your cellphone, if possible, two cellphones so one can take pictures and the other can record audio because in case you can't take notes of everything said due to the speed of the guests' speeches, you should have audio or a recorded audio that you can review when you get back to the station or the vehicle to create a news item. And always coordinate with your colleagues.
PARTICIPANT 9	kailangan gyud resilient ka ba because it's not a dream job lang no may mga tao na naga wait for you naga expect sa imo just to deliver good boost.	Yuy really need to be resilient because it's not just a dream job. There are people waiting for you, expecting you to deliver a good boost.

APPENDIX L**CURRICULUM VITAE****JENIE O. FAUNILLAN**

Bachelor of Arts In Communication

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Civil Status :Single

Gender :Female

Citizenship : Filipino

Height : 5'3 cm

Weight : 44kgs

Educational Attainment:

College : Davao Del Norte State College
Bachelor Of Arts In Communication
Fourth Year
Thesis Title: Behind the Mic: Experiences in Radio
Broadcasting Internship

Senior High School: La Filipina National High School
La Filipina, Tagum City, Ddn
2020-2021
Merit: With Honors

Secondary : La Filipina National High School
La Filipina, Tagum City, Ddn
2018-2019

Elementary : Florentino Catalan Elementary School
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2012-2013

Grants And Scholarships

2023-2024 TDP-TES Grantees batch 7.1

I hereby certify that the above-mentioned information is true and correct to the best of my knowledge and belief.

JENIE O. FAUNILLAN

Name with signature

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Date of Birth : June 30, 2002

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Weight : 51kgs

Educational Attainment:

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Fourth Year

Thesis Title: Behind the Mic: Experiences in Radio Broadcasting Internship

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Secondary : A.O Floirendo National High School
A.O Floirendo, Panabo City, Ddn
2018-2019

Elementary : Magsaysay Elementary School
Magsayay, Carmen Ddn
2012-2013

Grants And Scholarships

2021-2024 Iskolar Ng Lungsod- Ladderized

I hereby certify that the above-mentioned information is true and correct to the best of my knowledge and belief.

JEAH F. HERMOSO
Name with signature